

Block-Structured Prime Magic Squares: Orders 24, 25 and 26

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The work is also available at author's site:

<https://numbers-magic.com/?p=19518>

Abstract

*This work bring different ways of representing prime magic squares. These are of type: **blocks**, **block-bordered**, **concentric**, **nested**, etc. This work is for the orders 24, 25 and 26. For prime magic squares of orders 6 to 23 author's work [10, 11]. In case of prime magic squares of order 26, there is only example, i.e., four equal sum concentric primes magic squaers of order 13. The other examples are based on magic square of order 24. In this case, we constructed **block-bordered** prime magic squares, with internal blocks based on different types of prime magic squares of order 24.*

Keywords: magic squares, prime magic squares, block-wise magic squares, concentric magic squares, recreational mathematics.

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1 Introduction

During past years, the author studied block-wise constructions of magic squares. The work for the magic square of orders 8 to 47. Below are few examples:

1.1 Block-Wise Magic Squares of Order 8

Let's consider a **pandiagonal** of order 8 is given by

8x8	pan	260	260	260	260	260	260	260	260	260
260	7	60	1	62	15	52	9	54	260	260
260	2	61	8	59	10	53	16	51	260	260
260	64	3	58	5	56	11	50	13	260	260
260	57	6	63	4	49	14	55	12	260	260
260	23	44	17	46	31	36	25	38	260	260
260	18	45	24	43	26	37	32	35	260	260
260	48	19	42	21	40	27	34	29	260	260
	41	22	47	20	33	30	39	28	260	260
	260	260	260	260	260	260	260	260	260	260

It is composed four equal sums **pandiagonal** magic squares of order 4.

1.2 Block-Wise Magic Squares of Order 9

Let's consider a **pandiagonal** magic square of order 9 is given by

9x9	pan	369	369	369	369	369	369	369	369	369
369	22	71	30	27	64	32	20	69	34	369
369	35	21	67	28	23	72	33	25	65	369
369	66	31	26	68	36	19	70	29	24	369
369	40	8	75	45	1	77	38	6	79	369
369	80	39	4	73	41	9	78	43	2	369
369	3	76	44	5	81	37	7	74	42	369
369	58	53	12	63	46	14	56	51	16	369
369	17	57	49	10	59	54	15	61	47	369
	48	13	62	50	18	55	52	11	60	369
	369	369	369	369	369	369	369	369	369	369

In this case, blocks of order 3 are **semi-magic squares** (sum of only rows and columns) with equal magic sums.

Below is another example where blocks of order 3 are magic squares, but the magic square of order 9 is not **pandiagonal**:

9 mgc									369
31	36	29	76	81	74	13	18	11	369
30	32	34	75	77	79	12	14	16	369
35	28	33	80	73	78	17	10	15	369
22	27	20	40	45	38	58	63	56	369
21	23	25	39	41	43	57	59	61	369
26	19	24	44	37	42	62	55	60	369
67	72	65	4	9	2	49	54	47	369
66	68	70	3	5	7	48	50	52	369
71	64	69	8	1	6	53	46	51	369
369	369	369	369	369	369	369	369	369	369

In this case, blocks of order 3 are magic squares with different magic sums.

2 Block-Bordered Magic Squares of Order 10

Let's consider a magic square of order 10 with inner part as magic square of order 8 with blocks of order 4 is given by

10x10	mgc									505	
	91	86	16	84	18	14	4	98	2	92	505
	13	47 58 19 78				39 66 27 70				88	505
	89	22	75	50	55	30	67	42	63	12	505
	11	82	23	54	43	74	31	62	35	90	505
	96	51	46	79	26	59	38	71	34	5	505
	1	48	57	20	77	40	65	28	69	100	505
	93	21	76	49	56	29	68	41	64	8	505
	7	81	24	53	44	73	32	61	36	94	505
	95	52	45	80	25	60	37	72	33	6	505
	9	15	85	17	83	87	97	3	99	10	505
	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505

The blocks of order 8 are equal sums pandiagonal magic squares of order 10.

2.1 Block-Bordered Magic Squares of Order 11

The **block-bordered** magic square of order 11 with inner part as magic square of order 9 is given by

11x11	mgc											671
	12	20	18	16	14	113	114	116	118	120	10	671
	121	21	38	43	55	60	68	80	85	99	1	671
	119	53	58	72	75	92	97	28	33	41	3	671
	117	82	87	95	26	31	45	48	65	70	5	671
	115	47	25	30	69	50	64	94	81	89	7	671
	11	67	54	62	101	79	84	42	23	37	111	671
	13	96	77	91	40	27	35	74	52	57	109	671
	15	34	39	29	59	73	51	90	98	76	107	671
	17	63	71	49	88	93	83	32	46	24	105	671
	19	86	100	78	36	44	22	61	66	56	103	671
	112	102	104	106	108	9	8	6	4	2	110	671
	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671

The blocks of order 8 are equal sums **pandiagonal** magic squares of order 10.

2.2 Block-Wise Magic Squares of Order 12

Below are three different ways of writing **block-wise** magic squares of order 12. First as magic square formed by 16 blocks of magic squares of order 3 with different magic sums. Second as magic square formed by 9 blocks of **pandiagonal** magic squares of order 4 with equal magic sums. Third as 4 blocks of order 6 with equal magic sums. In the first two cases, the magic square of order 12 is **pandiagonal**, while third case, it is just a magic square.

• **Blocks of Order 3**

12x12	pan	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870
870	98	1	51	72	22	119	78	28	125	140	43	93	870
870	3	50	97	118	71	24	124	77	30	45	92	139	870
870	49	99	2	23	120	70	29	126	76	91	141	44	870
870	131	34	84	87	37	134	57	7	104	113	16	66	870
870	36	83	130	133	86	39	103	56	9	18	65	112	870
870	82	132	35	38	135	85	8	105	55	64	114	17	870
870	67	117	20	5	102	52	47	144	94	73	123	26	870
870	21	68	115	100	53	6	142	95	48	27	74	121	870
870	116	19	69	54	4	101	96	46	143	122	25	75	870
870	88	138	41	32	129	79	14	111	61	58	108	11	870
870	42	89	136	127	80	33	109	62	15	12	59	106	870
870	137	40	90	81	31	128	63	13	110	107	10	60	870
	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870

• **Blocks of Order 4**

12x12	pan	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870
870	7	140	1	142	15	132	9	134	23	124	17	126	870
870	2	141	8	139	10	133	16	131	18	125	24	123	870
870	144	3	138	5	136	11	130	13	128	19	122	21	870
870	137	6	143	4	129	14	135	12	121	22	127	20	870
870	31	116	25	118	39	108	33	110	47	100	41	102	870
870	26	117	32	115	34	109	40	107	42	101	48	99	870
870	120	27	114	29	112	35	106	37	104	43	98	45	870
870	113	30	119	28	105	38	111	36	97	46	103	44	870
870	55	92	49	94	63	84	57	86	71	76	65	78	870
870	50	93	56	91	58	85	64	83	66	77	72	75	870
870	96	51	90	53	88	59	82	61	80	67	74	69	870
870	89	54	95	52	81	62	87	60	73	70	79	68	870
	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870

• Blocks of Order 6

12	mgc												870
	1	143	142	141	2	6	19	125	124	123	20	24	870
	138	8	136	9	11	133	120	26	118	27	29	115	870
	132	131	15	16	128	13	114	113	33	34	110	31	870
	18	14	129	130	17	127	36	32	111	112	35	109	870
	7	134	10	135	137	12	25	116	28	117	119	30	870
	139	5	3	4	140	144	121	23	21	22	122	126	870
	55	89	88	87	56	60	37	107	106	105	38	42	870
	84	62	82	63	65	79	102	44	100	45	47	97	870
	78	77	69	70	74	67	96	95	51	52	92	49	870
	72	68	75	76	71	73	54	50	93	94	53	91	870
	61	80	64	81	83	66	43	98	46	99	101	48	870
	85	59	57	58	86	90	103	41	39	40	104	108	870
	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870

More on these kind of magic squares can be seen in author’s work [28, 29, 30]. The aim of this work write magic squares with blocks of order 4 with distinct prime number entries.

Based on the idea of blocks, block-borders, etc. given above,we shall concentrate our work in this direction on **prime magic squares**. This whole work is given in many parts.

3 Block-Structured Prime Magic Squares of Orders 24, 25 and 26

This work brings different ways representing magic squares in prime numbers. Initial aim is represent in terms of blocks. Some of possibilities led us to concentric or single-layer bordered magic squares. It includes blocks of orders 3, 4, 5, etc. Sometimes these blocks are of **equal** or **different** magic sums. This work is for the orders 6 to 14. In case of order 10, 11, 13, 14, etc, we don’t have division in blocks but we represent them as block-bordered. This means there are one or two layers of border, while the internal part is as blocks of small orders.

Whenever, we write **prime magic square**, it means that the magic squares are composed of **distinct prime number entries**, except in few cases, we the central constant 1000003 is repeating. This constant generally goes up to certain order,i.e, around order 120. For orders higher than this, the next central constant is used. It is only in case of odd order primes magic squares.

This work is for the **prime magic squares** of orders 24, 25 and 26. The table below give different representations for each order:

Order	Representations
24	10 (01-10)
25	04 (11-14)
26	11 (15-25)
Total	25

3.1 Prime Magic Squares of Order 24

Below are few examples of prime magic squares of order 24 with different representations.

Example 1. Equal Sums Blocks of Order 12 Composed of Different Sums of Order 3 Let's consider a following prime magic square of order 24:

811879	524287	1808761	386143	255679	891907	1152799	744397	2569093	769207	476167	1609717	667333	423463	1449673	327133	213133	738313	1210879	787207	2723353	874597	576889	2008063
2045191	1048309	51427	1017007	511243	5479	2905057	1488763	72469	1792207	951697	111187	1629163	846823	64483	837373	426193	15013	3086287	1573813	61339	2286649	1153183	19717
287857	1572331	1284739	130579	766807	636343	408433	2233129	1824727	293677	1427227	1134187	243973	1270183	1026313	114073	639253	525253	424273	2360419	1936747	298303	1729477	1431769
819937	511447	1737007	971077	606313	2060161	610447	393961	1358059	764611	488617	1678399	691813	454513	1580533	597679	393109	1367539	961141	607093	2073457	912403	545773	1814983
1939867	1022797	105727	2301601	1212517	123433	1535101	787489	39877	1890997	977209	63421	1797673	908953	20233	1555969	786109	16249	2326213	1213897	101581	1993633	1091053	188473
308587	1534147	1225657	364873	1818721	1453957	216919	1181017	964531	276019	1465801	1189807	237373	1363393	1126093	204679	1179109	974539	354337	1820701	1466653	367123	1636333	1269703
1062349	596599	1919689	1174099	762499	2637799	375757	237607	812257	657313	403861	1360207	1206181	764293	2614237	687823	458629	1604347	872863	541543	1834813	365509	235891	813907
2050219	1192879	335539	2988499	1524799	61099	911707	475207	38707	1510021	807127	104233	2936293	1528237	120181	1833457	916933	409	2045023	1083073	121123	920167	471769	23371
466069	1789159	1323409	411799	2287099	1875499	138157	712807	574657	254047	1210393	956941	442237	2292181	1850293	229519	1375237	1146043	331333	1624603	1293283	129631	707647	578029
686947	368197	1152937	602233	376009	1276117	959953	624517	2161189	959779	632089	2200069	567319	358867	1221811	1426237	935461	3250633	103669	64717	219301	994711	642133	2215177
1202017	736027	270037	1425337	751453	77569	2449789	1248553	47317	2504269	1263979	23689	1370491	715999	61507	3695173	1870777	46381	244861	129229	13597	2504473	1284007	63541
319117	1103857	785107	226789	1126897	900673	335917	1872589	1537153	327889	1895869	1568179	210187	1073131	864679	490921	2806093	2315317	39157	193741	154789	352837	1925881	1573303
790927	502501	1720909	415153	205603	612823	1233763	794407	2738269	887017	497671	1600993	530227	338893	1163821	585073	335893	1093633	1011343	664273	2309803	1065109	661417	2240551
1934761	1004779	74797	608863	411193	213523	3093319	1588813	84307	1709203	995227	281251	1311241	677647	44053	1180093	671533	162973	2626933	1328473	30013	2497801	1322359	146917
288649	1507057	1218631	209563	616783	407233	439357	2383219	1943863	389461	1492783	1103437	191473	1016401	825067	249433	1007173	757993	347143	1992673	1645603	404167	1983301	1579609
498523	313477	1068499	866083	505459	1659877	847543	495043	1626013	1043683	686773	2389063	1087027	689257	2358877	778699	485977	1650031	784627	514357	1786327	511939	310819	1042099
1196809	626833	56857	1804267	1010473	216679	1768003	989533	211063	2718553	1373173	27793	2650237	1378387	106537	1842901	971569	100237	2030137	1028437	26737	1151779	621619	91459
185167	940189	755143	361069	1515487	1154863	353053	1484023	1131523	357283	2059573	1702663	397897	2067517	1669747	293107	1457161	1164439	270547	1542517	1272247	201139	932419	731299
926467	609277	2119717	663541	432907	1499569	903457	567367	1933177	600169	390781	1353607	1442899	691231	2013127	846751	544123	1872097	736249	456349	1544449	463537	308923	1080301
2411737	1218487	25237	1701367	865339	29311	2164387	1134667	104947	1534957	781519	28081	1952647	1382419	812191	2113003	1087657	62311	1720549	912349	104149	1234351	617587	823
317257	1827697	1510507	231109	1297771	1067137	336157	1701967	1365877	209431	1172257	962869	751711	2073607	1321939	303217	1631191	1328563	280249	1368349	1088449	154873	926251	771637
862447	574969	2012323	1288891	856693	2993437	290419	143719	426859	670303	425197	1454779	422479	280909	981289	959209	634717	2213833	562519	365527	1264213	1084777	719227	2511337
2299789	1149913	37	3417553	1713007	8461	423439	286999	150559	1634569	850093	65617	1120369	561559	2749	2523877	1269253	14629	1432447	730753	29059	2865007	1438447	11887
287503	1724857	1437379	432577	2569321	2137123	147139	430279	283579	245407	1274989	1029883	141829	842209	700639	324673	1903789	1579297	197293	1095979	898987	365557	2157667	1792117

It is **block-structured prime magic square** of order 24. It is composed of four **equal sums** prime magic square 12. Each block of order 12 is again composed of 16 **different sums** prime magic squares of order 3. In this case the magic squares sums are

$$S_{24 \times 24} := 24000072 \text{ and } S_{12 \times 12} := 12000036$$

Example 2. Equal Sums Blocks of Order 3 Let's consider a following prime magic square of order 24:

869983	857737	1272289	1376899	311677	1311433	1465993	802297	731719	991777	1978219	30013	758617	1532449	708943	854713	644653	1500643	570373	1167847	1261789	576379	1867147	556483
1402309	1000003	597697	934537	1000003	1065469	265729	1000003	1734277	38239	1000003	1961767	950329	1000003	1049677	1645933	1000003	354073	1691419	1000003	308587	980107	1000003	1019899
727717	1142269	1130023	688573	1688329	623107	1268287	1197709	534013	1969993	21787	1008229	1291063	467557	1241389	499363	1355353	1145293	738217	832159	1429633	1443523	132859	1423627
136777	1736269	1126963	674833	1637773	687403	848839	661777	1489393	1718083	208213	1073713	1046413	832339	1121257	978883	819187	1201939	556609	997897	1445503	989803	652453	1357753
1990189	1000003	9817	1012573	1000003	987433	1640557	1000003	359449	355633	1000003	1644373	1074847	1000003	925159	1223059	1000003	776947	1888897	1000003	111109	1367953	1000003	632053
873043	263737	1863229	1312603	362233	1325173	510613	1338229	1151167	926293	1791793	281923	878749	1167667	953593	798067	1180819	1021123	554503	1002109	1443397	642253	1347553	1010203
1072957	404119	1522933	1094089	12697	1893223	474583	1118599	1406827	932983	142057	1924969	1030957	1776499	192553	1055233	1013239	931537	1324033	1166413	509563	1728409	44617	1226983
1449979	1000003	550027	1799137	1000003	200869	1932247	1000003	67759	1991989	1000003	8017	161599	1000003	1838407	876307	1000003	1123699	185533	1000003	1814473	498577	1000003	1501429
477073	1595887	927049	106783	1987309	905917	593179	881407	1525423	75037	1857949	1067023	1807453	223507	969049	1068469	986767	944773	1490443	833593	675973	773023	1955389	271597
1845133	49117	1105759	723259	965197	1311553	693733	848593	1457683	650599	1238197	1111213	1937323	41299	1021387	942889	421987	1635133	434989	1639357	925663	1136719	1437097	426193
260629	1000003	1739377	1588297	1000003	411709	1763953	1000003	236053	1460617	1000003	539389	84067	1000003	1915939	1692247	1000003	307759	1490677	1000003	509329	289477	1000003	1710529
894247	1950889	154873	688453	1034809	1276747	542323	1151413	1306273	888793	761809	1349407	978619	1958707	62683	364873	1578019	1057117	1074343	360649	1565017	1573813	562909	863287
1330873	945409	723727	1523407	848959	627643	626323	1524637	849049	1317853	721219	960937	1042597	963709	993703	1438303	815047	746659	820273	627139	1552597	1177453	902347	920209
392857	1000003	1607149	104239	1000003	1895767	1222729	1000003	777277	643087	1000003	1356919	951109	1000003	1048897	308359	1000003	1691647	1732327	1000003	267679	742759	1000003	1257247
1276279	1054597	669133	1372363	1151047	476599	1150957	475369	1373683	1039069	1278787	682153	1006303	1036297	957409	1253347	1184959	561703	447409	1372867	1179733	1079797	1097659	822553
662443	847009	1490557	893413	1091047	1015549	930199	1992937	76873	1143013	1323997	532999	478243	1321513	1200253	575647	1278619	1145743	1193503	280243	1526263	603349	1860637	536023
1828117	1000003	171889	1122139	1000003	877867	146677	1000003	1853329	389989	1000003	1610017	1722013	1000003	277993	1570099	1000003	429907	1332763	1000003	667243	932677	1000003	1067329
509449	1152997	1337563	984457	908959	1106593	1923133	7069	1069807	1467007	676009	856993	799753	678493	1521763	854263	721387	1424359	473743	1719763	806503	1463983	139369	1396657
499033	1239013	1261963	1060519	196927	1742563	1329703	1252729	417577	630613	1645537	723859	790033	1521193	688783	381673	1836979	781357	1054429	69127	1876453	885097	1863559	251353
1762933	1000003	237073	1682047	1000003	317959	87877	1000003	1912129	1093249	1000003	906757	898753	1000003	1101253	1399687	1000003	600319	1822027	1000003	177979	366259	1000003	1633747
738043	760993	1500973	257443	1803079	939487	1582429	747277	670303	1276147	354469	1369393	1311223	478813	1209973	1218649	163027	1618333	123553	1930879	945577	1748653	136447	1114909
1930603	3457	1065949	1460377	1041109	498523	1002553	1876009	121447	933313	1857967	208729	718813	620623	1660573	860383	295129	1844497	1820977	172519	1006513	239803	1780027	980179
135349	1000003	1864657	38149	1000003	1961857	118897	1000003	1881109	275419	1000003	1724587	1941763	1000003	58243	1984117	1000003	15889	185539	1000003	1814467	1740379	1000003	259627
934057	1996549	69403	1501483	958897	539629	1878559	123997	997453	1791277	142039	1066693	339433	1379383	1281193	155509	1704877	1139623	993493	1827487	179029	1019827	219979	1760203

It is **block-structured prime magic square** of order 24 composed of all **equal sums** blocks of order 3. In order to bring these **equal sums** we used the idea of fixed prime 1000003 in each block of order 3. In this case the magic squares sums are

$$S_{24 \times 24} := 24000072 \text{ and } S_{3 \times 3} := 3000009$$

Example 3. Equal Sums Blocks of Order 12 Composed of Different Sums of Order 4 Let's consider a following prime magic square of order 24:

907759	1051417	757909	901567	556093	1232713	474241	1150861	574657	1659919	823819	1909081	1801489	1431733	1547773	1178017	788383	644089	567097	422803	1336333	1159843	649483	472993
1120237	626623	1182703	689089	1255021	1099741	607213	451933	1867231	958021	1525717	616507	1080913	1767307	1212199	1898593	402817	933703	277483	808369	591709	412387	1396939	1217617
378733	322459	1486867	1430593	868561	921601	785353	838393	1545769	552859	1930879	937969	1720867	2213053	766453	1258639	289669	780583	430603	921517	1389163	1447273	362053	420163
1211923	1618153	191173	597403	734233	159853	1547101	972721	979819	1796677	687061	1503919	1355743	546919	2432587	1623763	941503	63997	1147189	269683	301447	599149	1210177	1507879
1289557	952507	1721911	1384861	1099723	1445047	554959	900283	486667	564667	760927	838927	360457	190339	639487	469369	1343029	858883	1141123	656977	1342093	1897807	1272379	1828093
1533331	889081	1785337	1141087	431863	1265053	734953	1568143	804091	911227	414367	521503	293599	657583	172243	536227	829987	711577	1288429	1170019	1938829	721213	2448973	1231357
1353487	1006177	1668241	1320931	1066063	962413	1037593	933943	1026457	1063921	261673	299137	350899	363343	466483	478927	928099	1155709	844297	1071907	2138377	1142233	2027953	1031809
1172461	2501071	173347	1501957	1402363	327499	1672507	597643	333973	111373	1214221	991621	654697	448387	381439	175129	898897	1273843	726163	1101109	921073	2579119	591067	2249113
978157	1172257	344017	538117	1530691	840571	1452487	762367	863299	998917	1191769	1327387	1081687	541237	1649449	1108999	672883	1800529	988297	2115943	385537	271867	748639	634969
339673	968911	547363	1176601	945577	1154017	1139041	1347481	1418797	1508449	682237	771889	1351069	880723	1309963	839617	1585219	1748407	1040419	1203607	665479	797593	222913	355027
560317	792667	723607	955957	1195021	1769881	523177	1098037	1024357	1296829	893857	1166329	1298719	1312513	878173	891967	1951153	1052893	1735933	837673	255499	448633	571873	765007
1154401	98713	1417561	361873	914827	821647	1471411	1378231	1074919	577177	1613509	1115767	649897	1646899	543787	1540789	1368397	975823	1813003	1420429	734497	522919	497587	286009
1347001	653893	2132941	1439833	857569	779899	421159	343489	1123699	1352557	659569	888427	1114039	1686403	510943	1083307	166783	249763	528691	611671	2062759	980149	2044069	961459
1190851	2097763	689071	1595983	883357	516709	684349	317701	1062367	818383	1193743	949759	668677	1006237	1191109	1528669	419191	527701	250753	359263	907891	1256149	1768069	2116327
1635163	2044111	742723	1151671	389161	1102249	98809	811897	1007047	1110943	901183	1005079	1025509	533809	1663537	1171837	334603	58153	720301	443851	2371627	2612749	411469	652591
1400653	777901	2008933	1386181	272029	3259	1197799	929029	831139	742369	1269757	1180987	1586467	1168243	1029103	610879	636331	721291	57163	142123	706159	1199389	1824829	2318059
640531	583087	642211	584767	1241557	670333	1329673	758449	1692697	1160953	1613761	1082017	740527	1413877	1413001	2086351	1177243	473419	1526587	822763	545497	838963	334171	627637
520309	310927	914371	704989	1380727	931789	1068217	619279	896263	1955251	819463	1878451	1946809	1604821	1222057	880069	1058839	1369393	630613	941167	796981	443761	729373	376153
946489	608191	617107	278809	727459	1523077	476929	1272547	653281	1340761	1433953	2121433	934051	312979	2513899	1892827	1046827	1829533	170473	953179	903493	888961	284173	269641
343267	948391	276907	882031	650269	874813	1125193	1349737	2307187	1092463	1682251	467527	2032369	2322079	504799	794509	717103	327667	1672339	1282903	100297	174583	998551	1072837
1356499	666403	1321483	631387	568903	1245781	1553173	2230051	413089	951109	262069	800089	438133	458323	517471	537661	1948927	914467	2307091	1272631	1002523	525529	1277137	800143
711847	1447807	540079	1276039	1398367	2112007	686947	1400587	618439	356869	856309	594739	645481	464617	511177	330313	977671	1556551	1665007	2243887	637669	551917	1250749	1164997
835489	1732369	255517	1152397	1480771	531043	2267911	1318183	969757	344887	868291	243421	675601	710377	265417	300193	1190149	1179109	2042449	2031409	1366693	955993	846673	435973
1071937	129193	1858693	915949	2149867	1709077	1089877	649087	425071	773491	439687	788107	192373	318271	657523	783421	2326369	2792989	428569	895189	598447	1571893	230773	1204219

It is **block-structured prime magic square** of order 24. It is composed of four **equal sums** prime magic square 12. Each block of order 12 is again composed of 9 **different sums** prime magic squares of order 4. In this case the magic squares sums are

$$S_{24 \times 24} := 24000072 \text{ and } S_{12 \times 12} := 12000036$$

Example 4. Equal Sums Blocks of Order 4 Let's consider a following prime magic square of order 24:

1688179	307669	1692337	311827	1693303	309223	1690783	306703	1695283	310729	1689277	304723	1698013	308317	1691689	301993	1130953	873469	1126537	869053	1131553	869983	1130023	868453
315517	1998397	1609	1684489	313333	1993273	6733	1686673	314239	1991293	8713	1685767	312709	1988563	11443	1687297	873913	1994827	5179	1126093	875803	1994227	5779	1124203
733	1690993	309013	1999273	439	1693639	306367	1999567	457	1696543	303463	1999549	1063	1698349	301657	1998943	709	1131343	868663	1999297	139	1133263	866743	1999867
1995583	2953	1997053	4423	1992937	3877	1996129	7069	1990033	1447	1998559	9973	1988227	4783	1995223	11779	1994437	373	1999633	5569	1992517	2539	1997467	7489
1294123	706633	1293373	705883	1299583	706267	1293739	700423	1306519	710293	1289713	693487	1344199	652237	1347769	655807	1358779	645937	1354069	641227	1387129	651517	1348489	612877
710257	1994479	5527	1289749	707467	1989019	10987	1292539	695917	1982083	17923	1304089	659047	1996459	3547	1340959	660277	1981879	18127	1339729	635287	1953529	46477	1364719
3643	1296613	703393	1996363	4993	1300633	699373	1995013	15823	1306849	693157	1984183	1987	1345879	654127	1998019	37	1359739	640267	1999969	26497	1389559	610447	1973509
1991989	2287	1997719	8017	1987969	4093	1995913	12037	1981753	787	1999219	18253	1994779	5437	1994569	5227	1980919	12457	1987549	19087	1951099	5407	1994599	48907
1174759	836449	1163557	825247	1113877	893029	1106977	886129	1125127	897469	1102537	874879	1130047	890119	1109887	869959	1153777	875209	1124797	846229	1500643	517243	1482763	499363
831367	1977817	22189	1168639	906649	1974787	25219	1093357	905449	1963537	36469	1094557	904759	1958617	41389	1095247	905959	1934887	65119	1094047	504943	1976239	23767	1495063
19483	1178173	821833	1980523	14629	1123807	876199	1985377	10729	1129957	870049	1989277	19609	1143067	856939	1980397	19249	1167637	832369	1980757	19777	1502233	497773	1980229
1974403	7573	1992433	25603	1964857	8389	1991617	35149	1958707	9049	1990957	41299	1945597	8209	1991797	54409	1921027	22279	1977727	78979	1974649	4297	1995709	25357
1381459	643969	1356037	618547	1018873	987997	1012009	981133	1019449	998443	1001563	980557	1032679	983407	1016599	967327	1039069	979423	1020583	960937	1007023	991633	1008373	992983
626317	1965973	34033	1373689	995227	1726939	273067	1004779	982687	1726363	273643	1017319	983863	1713133	286873	1016143	984457	1706743	293263	1015549	990163	1747087	252919	1009843
27337	1382533	617473	1972669	259219	1019119	980887	1740787	277687	1025623	974383	1722319	273997	1036339	963667	1726009	272257	1041583	958423	1727749	260809	1012093	987913	1739197
1964899	7537	1992469	35107	1726693	265957	1734049	273313	1720189	249583	1750423	279817	1709473	267133	1732873	290533	1704229	272263	1727743	295777	1742017	249199	1750807	257989
1875859	127453	1872553	124147	1879243	138427	1861579	120763	1538029	435637	1564369	461977	1578289	453367	1546639	421717	1581649	454387	1545619	418357	1590739	429277	1570729	409267
148747	1970407	29599	1851259	150583	1967023	32983	1849423	475927	1974559	25447	1524079	449557	1934299	65707	1550449	432007	1930939	69067	1567999	471607	1921849	78157	1528399
7459	1878319	121687	1992547	3769	1879849	120157	1996237	29287	1555819	444187	1970719	39217	1579639	420367	1960789	57697	1583929	416077	1942309	19927	1594849	405157	1980079
1967947	23833	1976173	32059	1966417	14713	1985293	33589	1956769	33997	1966009	43237	1932949	32707	1967299	67057	1928659	30757	1969249	71347	1917739	54037	1945969	82267
1032007	982393	1017613	967999	1051153	943429	1056577	948853	1065313	950029	1049977	934693	1404883	622159	1377847	595123	1413283	600469	1399537	586723	1421083	610339	1389667	578923
962503	1370263	629743	1037503	981577	1351117	648889	1018429	987457	1336957	663049	1012549	611263	1950577	49429	1388743	624199	1942177	57829	1375807	612223	1934377	65629	1387783
650059	1046827	953179	1349947	627379	1062367	937639	1372627	614569	1069597	930409	1385437	35089	1406683	593323	1964917	26317	1419247	580759	1973689	33343	1422097	577909	1966663
1355443	600529	1399477	644563	1339903	643099	1356907	660103	1332673	643429	1356577	667333	1948777	20593	1979413	51229	1936213	38119	1961887	63793	1933363	33199	1966807	66643

It is **block-structured prime magic square** of order 24 composed of all **equal sums** blocks of order 4. In this case the magic squares sums are

$$S_{24 \times 24} := 24000072 \text{ and } S_{4 \times 4} := 4000012$$

Example 5. Different Sums Blocks of Order 6 with Different Sums Blocks of Order 4 Let's consider a following prime magic square of order 24:

1445071	1112047	1597129	411751	1767427	1163689	769309	1754527	1761553	1565269	819457	2549203	755863	696427	154699	605503	379087	189139	414451	738391	874213	1008913	457117	1009837
622777	1452439	1038727	1460311	1046599	1876261	1855999	1463587	2126617	946489	1609519	1217107	245989	483643	564463	362443	443263	680917	370477	876373	1111447	389527	624601	1130497
1812091	1140157	1128811	1370227	1358881	686947	2090317	825547	1719049	1354057	2247559	982789	372829	199447	674683	252223	727459	554077	532537	891487	400321	1100653	609487	968437
2077849	1933171	2108941	390097	565867	421189	1704763	1868989	1194547	1878559	1204117	1368343	342187	487603	475207	451699	439303	584719	1200253	451837	494443	1006531	1049137	300721
203977	472309	721597	1777441	2026729	2295061	2275027	1988089	1105999	1967107	1085017	798079	326083	683119	139459	787447	243787	600823	1494067	782251	995737	505237	718723	6907
1335349	1386991	901909	2087287	731611	1053967	523903	1318579	1311553	1507837	2253649	2303797	737767	230479	772207	321403	547819	171043	491137	762583	626761	492061	1043857	1086523
544837	627901	1273231	1194769	361159	1267897	664711	858877	880687	1162261	346543	1005643	391441	376837	1573699	1269757	1224739	2244841	350851	848593	1315453	1287133	987391	1940821
1021159	1343767	1390801	365797	412831	735439	965113	609361	1266631	372943	1030213	674461	1863157	699931	1533211	827227	1660507	497281	1819591	862117	908671	1334743	1381297	423823
383101	693619	459691	1296907	1062979	1373497	1266301	777313	769273	870301	862261	373273	1788571	1701757	1225657	1134781	658681	571867	1104373	1714441	1343413	900001	528973	1139041
1200937	474949	802597	954001	1281649	555661	653623	866707	352867	1286707	772867	985951	1997587	500947	107347	2253091	1859491	362851	1098211	637723	932983	1310431	1605691	1145203
1631059	1000861	860107	896491	755737	125539	735043	1025767	890377	749197	613807	904531	924961	1818241	1854661	505777	542197	1435477	2054623	1272547	1301761	941653	970867	188791
488701	1128697	483367	561829	1395439	1211761	633931	780697	758887	477313	1293031	974863	115597	1983601	786739	1090681	1135699	1968997	302593	1394821	927961	956281	1256023	1892563
788167	948847	1055437	380251	917887	826333	1507657	924829	420241	1451059	1358221	437587	1742413	1369561	440227	1108057	1104781	135403	1507879	1692511	894721	528709	1649917	809377
564097	986941	1256407	382567	652033	1074877	668617	1145371	902389	1130809	887827	1364581	459703	799621	560281	1406533	1167193	1507111	728269	560149	746791	1614247	1800889	1632769
774853	490993	681253	957721	1147981	864121	1343161	796387	886177	1147021	1236811	690037	921751	1520083	1120153	846661	446731	1045063	1047127	1240081	1779889	581149	1120957	1313911
1198201	624577	492757	1146217	1014397	440773	860791	451621	358531	1674667	1581577	1172407	904693	1025257	1331107	635707	941557	1062121	1645867	1301467	719659	1641379	1059571	715171
778963	1175437	847531	791443	463537	860011	123757	1673017	1919299	113899	360181	1909441	40471	588667	922087	1044727	1378147	1926343	602311	1620379	1475737	885301	740659	1758727
812641	690127	583537	1258723	721087	850807	1595611	1108369	1612957	582139	674977	525541	1831411	597253	1526587	858757	862033	224401	1551661	668527	1466317	1832329	711121	853159
1254217	1708387	1733827	369133	1027591	223087	148609	977407	504247	210247	944689	977239	456457	1701019	1754419	1372999	618577	2334127	1724551	898069	1169257	1042519	652627	196771
1227547	618463	1190587	914827	1486951	877867	829063	439273	355819	898327	814873	425083	2110519	720289	2129227	616639	2025577	635347	434989	461359	459937	1434661	1433239	1459609
1083451	1649887	1065901	1039513	455527	1021963	1025347	466537	820333	433813	787609	228799	2184769	2088907	661099	2084767	656959	561097	605887	1500019	1348309	546289	394579	1288711
356533	1193011	934897	1170517	912403	1748881	339289	772339	429463	824683	481807	914857	1226767	1594297	293149	2452717	1151569	1519099	508789	463921	445771	1448827	1430677	1385809
512167	749467	1019443	1085971	1355947	1593247	1143223	830143	902677	351469	424003	110923	1847347	1088239	2408257	337609	1657627	898519	711751	1363897	1535179	359419	530701	1182847
1882327	397027	371587	1736281	1077823	851197	276907	276739	749899	1043899	309457	1105537	411739	1044847	991447	1372867	2127289	2289409	1697827	996529	725341	852079	1241971	170047

It is **block-structured prime magic square** of order 24. It is composed of **different sums concentric prime magic square** of order 6. The internal blocks of order 4 are also prime magic squares of order 4 with **different sums**. In this case the magic square sum is

$$S_{24 \times 24} := 24000072$$

Example 6. Equal Sums Blocks of Order 6 with Equal Sums Blocks of Order 4 Let's consider a following prime magic square of order 24:

It is **block-structured prime magic square** of order 24. It is composed of **equal sums concentric prime magic square** of order 6. The internal blocks of order 4 are also prime magic squares of order 4 with **equal sums**. In this case the magic squares sums are

$$S_{24 \times 24} := 24000072 \text{ and } S_{6 \times 6} := 6000018$$

Example 7. Different Sums Blocks of Order 8 with Different Sums Blocks of Orders 6 and 4 Let's consider a following prime magic square of order 24:

219217	1409407	1611763	1761169	1814809	467899	2154907	2885173	404011	341491	633307	157639	674161	336361	502651	398611	1635163	326947	1662943	1716181	665221	1067047	549391	604603
2371423	2193973	517729	1871923	1262887	2407003	989743	709663	356731	802651	569617	338707	592357	248461	34381	505327	618637	359767	1375111	386041	688063	1446007	1915633	1438237
2365309	2206819	1968979	1948483	1132603	1112107	874267	715777	325747	303937	481417	566149	295909	380641	558121	536311	310111	1112143	1154737	1227151	829723	902137	944731	1746763
794203	1003957	1667599	1569817	1511269	1413487	2077129	2286883	169129	140839	214141	546961	315097	647917	721219	692929	769033	1046257	1287067	1150057	906817	769807	1010617	1287841
2069737	717139	736927	1750129	1330957	2344159	2363947	1011349	712429	407899	280717	280537	581521	581341	454159	149629	1576921	1689343	1026043	1658893	397981	1030831	367531	479953
2110183	1030027	1788667	893743	2187343	1292419	2051059	970903	605497	103171	747841	330469	531589	114217	758887	256561	1712287	1821871	645901	77647	1979227	1410973	235003	344587
2198359	2091343	2563357	1209163	1818199	674083	887113	882727	411241	827677	292441	523351	269701	613597	59407	450817	153073	141241	681763	1670833	1368811	610867	1697107	1903801
195913	1671679	1469323	1319917	1266277	2613187	926179	2861869	463447	520567	228751	704419	187897	525697	359407	458047	1452271	1729927	393931	340693	1391653	989827	1507483	421711
953221	699073	424843	265471	373987	524743	660097	1741	645019	1516609	801337	1463563	1537513	300967	490579	1244437	2083297	681781	1094161	2052697	1556977	1278379	2325181	1024399
454213	733921	413863	673573	290041	672103	143881	521581	1216393	1054717	1358047	356197	988417	1544563	698077	783613	990349	2378119	1128931	2079787	486091	2063059	936667	2033869
259213	147727	446323	588481	387313	529471	828067	716581	1229827	624277	1041583	846739	1153267	958423	1375729	770179	511171	485347	2339929	743851	2280367	684289	2538871	2513047
336247	448387	556327	622927	352867	419467	527407	639547	1573813	1234777	1394893	642673	1357333	605113	765229	426193	2078431	567811	1226011	698977	2325241	1798207	2456407	945787
712837	596977	303571	423883	551911	672223	378817	262957	1039513	553369	407083	527803	1472203	1592923	1446637	960493	1742101	2245459	1396237	1952647	1071571	1627981	778759	1282117
171481	168457	645367	316297	659497	330427	807337	804313	1433353	1230949	1156453	1982797	17209	843553	769057	566653	1585447	1308367	1086259	2652961	371257	1937959	1715851	1438771
41911	831913	561931	302221	685753	303691	241873	933883	106537	1301929	641959	1643809	1011589	455443	945289	1893469	1106257	2087551	1895287	944431	2538127	961159	646099	1917961
974053	276721	550951	710323	601807	451051	315697	22573	755569	483397	1198669	536443	462493	1699039	1509427	1354987	1999819	2342437	1930057	971521	1467241	1745839	699037	940921
828547	933931	1592761	336157	838897	852889	1378081	1011289	1298191	632323	1394293	2438587	1834321	1992673	1166227	1795201	482569	653593	332803	461317	186157	688783	414199	456283
1064131	309577	874831	1516651	1219279	371179	1537897	879007	597613	1394671	2295793	1948327	823177	1425337	1526557	2540341	423289	307339	565483	512137	540187	236329	595303	495637
1223941	1265101	1117177	490891	1452247	825961	678037	719197	2537323	1521103	2201827	980503	2157451	936127	1616851	600631	728173	487447	429397	406993	511933	489529	431479	190753
1161169	1047979	1089469	1093129	850009	853669	895159	781969	2634301	756433	2045647	1310371	1827583	1092307	2381521	503653	501133	695089	539509	289243	629683	379417	223837	417793
1136869	1581487	458791	989467	953671	1484347	361651	806269	2531233	2314231	1161163	2644927	493027	1976791	823723	606721	289417	546097	696373	546067	372859	222553	372829	629509
315067	1220029	1220839	1312789	630349	722299	723109	1628071	1610251	1816027	867271	1340107	1797847	2270683	1321927	1527703	547537	397183	172573	595549	323377	746353	521743	371389
1110979	405241	1068307	426487	723859	1571959	1633561	832159	151	1611397	842161	1189627	2314777	1712617	1743283	3137803	240943	323623	353443	406789	378739	682597	611587	677983
931849	1009207	350377	1606981	1104241	1090249	565057	1114591	1342753	2505631	1743661	699367	1303633	1145281	1971727	1839763	462643	265333	586123	457609	732769	230143	504727	436357

It is **block-structured prime magic square** of order 24. It is composed of **different sums concentric prime magic square** of order 8. The internal blocks of orders 6 and 4 are also of **different sums** prime magic squares. In this case the magic square sum is

$$S_{24 \times 24} := 24000072$$

Example 8. Equal Sums Blocks of Order 8 with Different Sums Blocks of Orders 6 and 4 Let's consider a following prime magic square of order 24:

1595557	468859	1993759	1514179	120577	447463	813217	1046413	1595557	468859	1993759	1514179	120577	447463	813217	1046413	1595557	468859	1993759	1514179	120577	447463	813217	1046413
799063	1518709	114487	1896043	588433	1864417	17929	1200943	799063	1518709	114487	1896043	588433	1864417	17929	1200943	799063	1518709	114487	1896043	588433	1864417	17929	1200943
1230379	1573813	1033567	954043	1045963	966439	426193	769627	1230379	1573813	1033567	954043	1045963	966439	426193	769627	1230379	1573813	1033567	954043	1045963	966439	426193	769627
1476913	264529	1570099	1244029	755977	429907	1735477	523093	1476913	264529	1570099	1244029	755977	429907	1735477	523093	1476913	264529	1570099	1244029	755977	429907	1735477	523093
841207	660103	24763	906013	1093993	1975243	1339903	1158799	841207	660103	24763	906013	1093993	1975243	1339903	1158799	841207	660103	24763	906013	1093993	1975243	1339903	1158799
2539	787	1371583	895927	1104079	628423	1999219	1997467	2539	787	1371583	895927	1104079	628423	1999219	1997467	2539	787	1371583	895927	1104079	628423	1999219	1997467
1100773	1982077	1885519	103963	1411573	135589	481297	899233	1100773	1982077	1885519	103963	1411573	135589	481297	899233	1100773	1982077	1885519	103963	1411573	135589	481297	899233
953593	1531147	6247	485827	1879429	1552543	1186789	404449	953593	1531147	6247	485827	1879429	1552543	1186789	404449	953593	1531147	6247	485827	1879429	1552543	1186789	404449
1595557	468859	1993759	1514179	120577	447463	813217	1046413	1595557	468859	1993759	1514179	120577	447463	813217	1046413	1595557	468859	1993759	1514179	120577	447463	813217	1046413
799063	1518709	114487	1896043	588433	1864417	17929	1200943	799063	1518709	114487	1896043	588433	1864417	17929	1200943	799063	1518709	114487	1896043	588433	1864417	17929	1200943
1230379	1573813	1033567	954043	1045963	966439	426193	769627	1230379	1573813	1033567	954043	1045963	966439	426193	769627	1230379	1573813	1033567	954043	1045963	966439	426193	769627
1476913	264529	1570099	1244029	755977	429907	1735477	523093	1476913	264529	1570099	1244029	755977	429907	1735477	523093	1476913	264529	1570099	1244029	755977	429907	1735477	523093
841207	660103	24763	906013	1093993	1975243	1339903	1158799	841207	660103	24763	906013	1093993	1975243	1339903	1158799	841207	660103	24763	906013	1093993	1975243	1339903	1158799
2539	787	1371583	895927	1104079	628423	1999219	1997467	2539	787	1371583	895927	1104079	628423	1999219	1997467	2539	787	1371583	895927	1104079	628423	1999219	1997467
1100773	1982077	1885519	103963	1411573	135589	481297	899233	1100773	1982077	1885519	103963	1411573	135589	481297	899233	1100773	1982077	1885519	103963	1411573	135589	481297	899233
953593	1531147	6247	485827	1879429	1552543	1186789	404449	953593	1531147	6247	485827	1879429	1552543	1186789	404449	953593	1531147	6247	485827	1879429	1552543	1186789	404449
1595557	468859	1993759	1514179	120577	447463	813217	1046413	1595557	468859	1993759	1514179	120577	447463	813217	1046413	1595557	468859	1993759	1514179	120577	447463	813217	1046413
799063	1518709	114487	1896043	588433	1864417	17929	1200943	799063	1518709	114487	1896043	588433	1864417	17929	1200943	799063	1518709	114487	1896043	588433	1864417	17929	1200943
1230379	1573813	1033567	954043	1045963	966439	426193	769627	1230379	1573813	1033567	954043	1045963	966439	426193	769627	1230379	1573813	1033567	954043	1045963	966439	426193	769627
1476913	264529	1570099	1244029	755977	429907	1735477	523093	1476913	264529	1570099	1244029	755977	429907	1735477	523093	1476913	264529	1570099	1244029	755977	429907	1735477	523093
841207	660103	24763	906013	1093993	1975243	1339903	1158799	841207	660103	24763	906013	1093993	1975243	1339903	1158799	841207	660103	24763	906013	1093993	1975243	1339903	1158799
2539	787	1371583	895927	1104079	628423	1999219	1997467	2539	787	1371583	895927	1104079	628423	1999219	1997467	2539	787	1371583	895927	1104079	628423	1999219	1997467
1100773	1982077	1885519	103963	1411573	135589	481297	899233	1100773	1982077	1885519	103963	1411573	135589	481297	899233	1100773	1982077	1885519	103963	1411573	135589	481297	899233
953593	1531147	6247	485827	1879429	1552543	1186789	404449	953593	1531147	6247	485827	1879429	1552543	1186789	404449	953593	1531147	6247	485827	1879429	1552543	1186789	404449

It is **block-structured prime magic square** of order 24. It is composed of **equal sums concentric prime magic square** of order 8. The internal blocks of orders 6 and 4 are also of **equal sums** prime magic squares. In this case the magic squares sums are

$$S_{24 \times 24} := 24000072 \text{ and } S_{8 \times 8} := 8000024$$

Example 9. Concentric Equal Sums Blocks of Order 12 Let's consider a following prime magic square of order 24:

749083	1001839	1054267	1654369	1152667	1423579	319567	568273	1617739	511627	607357	1339669	1535467	1070197	1139683	390487	530539	753127	816559	1239457	1606897	1493677	984253	439693
388477	1359979	734047	1001989	1201309	554677	1514797	1005913	475789	1473847	677683	1611529	551269	1173553	505819	1302313	1647649	1579813	1308607	441703	807127	340129	893317	1448737
428299	814543	671533	421987	1545553	1392379	994927	863803	923053	1186789	1185463	1571707	1217677	449797	1834333	966619	616639	1703287	1085269	265423	1402147	126307	1550209	782329
1421977	1573753	1175173	1632979	469303	252277	1704187	1652419	288853	824833	426253	578029	877609	930409	457117	1561597	1264819	1152343	1034359	545023	441877	1542889	1069597	1122397
1610527	444883	1276183	869983	456517	1066693	933313	1543489	1130023	723823	1555123	389479	1379809	1576339	358417	830359	741283	1720123	279883	1258723	1169647	1641589	423667	620197
421609	1417279	1155919	330859	1488967	1376899	623107	511039	1669147	844087	582727	1578397	954697	1398289	478417	537793	1678429	388057	1611949	321577	1462213	1521589	601717	1045309
444967	1212397	328543	937537	1448449	1227337	772669	551557	1062469	1671463	787609	1555039	909409	553549	1614409	1397023	453913	2953	1997053	1546093	602983	385597	1446457	1090597
1627609	338347	1438447	517507	606079	329083	1670923	1393927	1482499	561559	1661659	372397	525373	821263	572683	115117	1126387	1888879	111127	873619	1884889	1427323	1178743	1474633
1065847	1391119	1141009	1711153	1530703	1747729	295819	347587	367027	858997	608887	934159	418843	1291489	810949	1558129	735187	847663	965647	1454983	438409	1189057	708517	1581163
1503967	125407	813217	1578019	454453	607627	1005079	1136203	1076953	1328473	1874599	496039	268993	698653	1873699	1033387	1383367	296719	914737	1734583	597859	165673	1301353	1731013
1677337	1322323	1265959	998017	798697	1445329	485209	994093	1524217	526159	640027	322669	1800577	1106689	1494187	697693	352357	420193	691399	1558303	1192879	1659877	826453	199429
660337	998167	945739	345637	847339	576427	1680439	1431733	382267	1488379	1392649	1250923	1560313	929809	860323	1609519	1469467	1246879	1183447	760549	393109	506329	1015753	464539
1012447	945409	1689379	1140913	280513	832297	1291447	1627147	415039	1275283	500839	989323	974497	1152937	1232713	1505929	929059	782539	1092283	755473	1473553	617983	433393	1049677
1219357	301657	1569859	582949	1630927	440677	1279303	1445929	292879	956083	1499767	780649	1482739	1982293	1546057	476587	1384087	492319	1607863	382189	914239	1127359	87037	517267
983863	294103	723949	322417	1564117	1488073	1084939	649879	905917	1260733	1705903	1016143	1484233	392923	1973557	1111087	870049	1565017	1197433	868849	401329	12703	1607083	515773
305839	1499053	661777	476467	1439287	1224529	832369	349369	1677997	1338229	500953	1694167	509563	1748269	1597423	1777939	1286773	1192369	542587	829813	370537	402583	251737	1490443
951583	1734547	722749	1291783	1640497	904573	1095433	359509	708223	1277257	265459	1048423	1325707	374203	388789	262807	1455379	717103	1282903	544627	1737199	1611217	1625803	674299
1118809	409267	305029	965047	394099	521923	1478083	1605907	1034959	1694977	1590739	881197	1388029	1257787	566857	1131223	273313	723967	1276039	1726693	868783	1433149	742219	611977
1647673	998539	1716427	1241389	1378579	1575583	424423	621427	758617	283579	1001467	352333	705967	881437	403729	1047997	1348987	1257013	742993	651019	952009	1596277	1118569	1294039
1401139	867577	1728457	1703323	586837	997933	1002073	1413169	296683	271549	1132429	598867	507589	365137	679807	150583	922333	1301929	698077	1077673	1849423	1320199	1634869	1492417
787099	1467589	1402363	322009	560719	775477	1167637	1650637	1523539	597643	532417	1212907	1555819	795763	402559	1629469	713233	807637	1457419	1170193	222067	1597447	1204243	444187
1125907	1927459	739273	1677589	435889	511933	915067	1350127	1094089	1276057	72547	874099	671557	289249	1987303	888919	1129957	434989	802573	1131157	1598677	26449	1710757	1328449
435637	500239	430147	1417057	369079	1559329	720703	554077	1707127	1043923	1698349	1564369	444007	1912969	453949	1523419	615919	1507687	392143	1617817	1085767	872647	17713	1555999
1010683	1054597	310627	859093	1719493	1167709	708559	372859	1584967	724723	1499167	987559	950329	847069	767293	494077	1070947	1217467	907723	1244533	526453	1382023	1566613	1025509

It is **block-structured prime magic square** of order 24. It is composed of **equal sums concentric prime magic square** of order 12. The internal blocks of orders 10, 8, 6 and 4 are also **equal sums** prime magic squares. In this case the magic squares sums are

$$S_{24 \times 24} := 24000072 \text{ and } S_{12 \times 12} := 12000036$$

Example 10. Single-Layer Bordered Prime Magic Square Let's consider a following prime magic square of order 24:

709817	54101	467549	94379	470651	13187	488981	218783	482519	304757	403757	142421	184721	354581	430799	440087	836807	954509	997889	951407	994199	995927	996539	11633
395189	289127	161753	239699	15671	287867	499679	412289	266153	66161	438953	126683	123203	126359	686339	967229	979949	826349	973151	989909	999431	999029	525017	604811
301583	496841	550757	119447	355799	73331	304631	376709	44519	69911	181439	250751	292427	967763	348353	971561	997961	852239	978821	996461	969929	297191	503159	698417
114041	77783	211811	199103	368939	382463	319811	87911	480587	467261	308051	423257	405047	472247	79601	849917	955313	979061	979211	999773	242447	788189	922217	885959
239711	335417	253823	247799	415697	422453	281993	198659	164987	154613	430427	147377	460337	357989	915623	969863	990323	915869	997589	176201	752201	746177	664583	760289
123407	21383	275921	255083	212183	799343	149867	64661	221603	23357	81233	145967	889937	901133	942749	774491	905453	976883	123323	787817	744917	724079	978617	876593
493001	302873	58229	341057	423209	54269	109001	192617	318161	246473	173429	133877	460829	836117	948581	996323	975083	609509	945731	576791	658943	941771	697127	506999
208889	149519	330689	362291	274019	352349	22643	124067	382763	251117	157841	421559	24419	982061	959723	783599	912851	977357	647651	725981	637709	669311	850481	791111
478637	182681	172259	354479	238991	113489	70997	19841	35801	71129	156089	167543	620657	997649	957701	993431	980159	929003	886511	761009	645521	827741	817319	521363
70439	428411	151703	299567	14723	266177	352511	157721	466073	881591	86783	124739	940271	457889	508727	533927	842279	647489	733823	985277	700433	848297	571589	929561
98573	109541	304553	31091	163847	30539	120299	364433	29201	149057	306191	65951	934049	693809	850943	970799	635567	879701	969461	836153	968909	695447	890459	901427
311237	48869	341597	89381	41513	2903	65921	447683	979373	194963	878651	799619	200381	121349	805037	20627	552317	934079	997097	958487	910619	658403	951131	688763
94049	91529	400523	282011	12413	277757	989939	804191	790379	349709	517901	808553	191447	482099	650291	209621	195809	10061	722243	987587	717989	599477	908471	905951
480419	222269	125201	441527	876077	982769	919823	997973	919067	933407	297257	325877	674123	702743	66593	80933	2027	80177	17231	123923	558473	874799	777731	519581
310043	993401	912083	867467	933209	812627	963701	998381	773537	491273	913217	875261	59729	542111	118409	226463	1619	36299	187373	66791	132533	87917	6599	689957
438233	829877	229127	926567	572927	782501	997793	998561	6569	928871	843911	832457	379343	2351	42299	964199	1439	2207	217499	427073	73433	770873	170123	561767
287501	951389	984119	556709	998633	705821	996881	87149	617237	748883	842159	578441	975581	17939	40277	216401	875933	3119	294179	1367	443291	15881	48611	712499
904847	994769	995747	997121	999239	942779	390491	807383	681839	753527	826571	866123	539171	163883	51419	3677	24917	890999	57221	761	2879	4253	5231	95153
987083	999863	999491	998681	999521	876677	850133	935339	778397	976643	918767	854033	110063	98867	57251	225509	94547	23117	200657	479	1319	509	137	12917
989687	999917	999749	992513	823799	577547	718007	801341	835013	845387	569573	852623	539663	642011	84377	30137	9677	84131	2411	584303	7487	251	83	10313
994013	999959	999809	757553	631061	617537	680189	912089	519413	532739	691949	576743	594953	527753	920399	150083	44687	20939	20789	227	800897	191	41	5987
992891	999599	702809	880553	644201	926669	695369	623291	955481	930089	818561	749249	707573	32237	651647	28439	2039	147761	21179	3539	30071	449243	401	7109
988343	474983	838247	760301	984329	712133	500321	587711	733847	933839	561047	873317	876797	873641	313661	32771	20051	173651	26849	10091	569	971	710873	11657
988367	945899	532451	905621	529349	986813	511019	781217	517481	695243	596243	857579	815279	645419	569201	559913	163193	45491	2111	48593	5801	4073	3461	290183

It is **concentric single-layer prime magic square** of order 24. The internal concentric single-layer prime magic square of order 22 is the same as given author's previous work [11]. In this case the magic square sum is

$$S_{24 \times 24} := 12000000$$

Remark 1. We observe that this the only magic square of order 24 with different magic sum. If want to have the same magic sum as of all the above magic squares of order 24, i.e., $S_{24 \times 24} := 24000072$, the reader can see the author's work [23]. In this work there two possibilities are given. The second one is exactly the same magic as all the above magic square. The reason depends on the internal 4 members we choose. The other entries comes proportionally.

3.2 Prime Magic Squares of Order 25

Below are few examples of prime magic squares of order 25 with different representations.

Example 11. Different Sums Blocks of Order 5 Let's consider a following prime magic square of order 25:

211639	1044781	191047	760147	942031	2294533	773611	1291117	1399441	101833	771481	352249	1824847	1317727	1319191	470167	1062013	1299289	272263	949033	369553	1568377	1675441	609601	2128663
786691	834709	521707	533371	473167	365527	1906237	407833	1202251	1978687	1499227	1056577	584281	1710439	734971	733489	1184143	697069	550447	887617	2145547	1632031	491983	1686967	395107
994051	328591	629929	931267	265807	703711	468121	1172107	1876093	1640503	463921	1770961	1117099	463237	1770277	652627	176857	810553	1444249	968479	1628203	1325263	1270327	1215391	912451
839437	726487	738151	425149	420421	254383	1141963	1936381	437977	2089831	1935859	523759	1649917	1177621	298339	1524409	1070659	924037	436963	96697	1796341	853687	2048671	908623	744313
317827	215077	1068811	499711	1048219	2242381	1570603	1053097	944773	49681	915007	1881949	409351	916471	1462717	672073	559093	321817	1348843	1150939	411991	972277	865213	1931053	2171101
837979	324637	1395661	1528687	581731	547999	980719	2111779	2090749	2141569	351931	410203	951943	972967	824641	1056217	1049677	1096399	268501	144751	697591	1600267	366907	1246513	1420057
1001839	1011559	296269	1493389	865639	1771459	1066999	1155907	2500783	1377667	1069687	1229227	303097	574687	334987	322339	761869	550117	857341	1123879	1475827	1303567	355441	1539793	656707
950269	1415569	933739	451909	917209	2280637	3008347	1574563	140779	868489	716827	47797	702337	1356877	687847	742891	818581	723109	627637	703327	853933	1302493	1066267	830041	1278601
592861	374089	1571209	855919	1274617	2265163	648343	1993219	2082127	883963	793207	829987	1101577	175447	611467	192631	588877	896101	684349	1253587	1591507	592741	1777093	828967	541027
1285747	1542841	471817	338791	1029499	1007557	2168407	1037347	1058377	2601127	580033	994471	452731	431707	1052743	1301467	396541	349819	1177717	390001	712477	532267	1765627	886021	1434943
168991	1447807	976117	1377451	2320729	44959	180379	92671	197959	226777	1644229	1581649	350947	1108363	314827	449203	2206207	2271163	892261	3438451	1369021	806263	1050727	380557	102367
2029051	1732117	460081	1582459	487387	207769	162391	104047	179209	89329	749083	971857	352069	1676083	1250923	2120551	1586791	1545553	2422027	1582363	649567	1174171	226753	824437	834007
1522897	1108561	1258219	1407877	993541	164767	165367	148549	131731	132331	419527	1704229	1000003	295777	1580479	2966767	2686693	1851457	1016221	736147	260137	392053	741787	1091521	1223437
2374447	933979	2056357	784321	141991	254929	117889	193051	134707	42169	501997	323923	1647937	1028149	1498009	3456301	1280887	2157361	2116123	246613	49003	659137	1256821	309403	1434571
195709	1068631	1540321	1138987	2347447	70321	116719	204427	99139	252139	1685179	418357	1649059	891643	355777	264463	1496707	1431751	2810653	3253711	1381207	677311	432847	1103017	114553
1720291	1623487	1611391	764689	1522387	1210477	1640941	890107	1490317	1152643	485497	1944067	629701	1727881	1701199	582139	210403	536287	516283	282103	678541	921157	593977	178693	385417
2201107	1422409	568207	2354731	695791	729217	2059441	432613	1338637	1824577	1726471	1967107	435571	1490329	868867	181123	251473	423559	601297	669763	479833	806203	260941	587527	623281
1676947	2380771	1448449	516127	1219951	2072773	556093	1276897	1997701	481021	926581	820891	1297669	1774447	1668757	643453	775267	425443	75619	207433	370003	332881	551557	770233	733111
269389	542167	2328691	1474489	2627509	970867	1215157	2121181	494353	1582927	2455657	1105009	2159767	628231	139681	151717	249589	427327	599413	699169	511711	515587	842173	296911	591403
1374511	1273411	1285507	2132209	1176607	1401151	912853	1663687	1063477	1343317	894139	651271	1965637	867457	2109841	568783	640483	314599	334603	268747	717697	181957	509137	924421	424573
1044217	469099	974749	960499	199831	1016641	328789	1239727	964207	590131	304687	1156747	1086607	318817	1547677	2357629	1711153	512047	1241659	124777	2235997	2031571	2011183	523777	47857
409327	720241	581227	887569	1050031	333049	667519	507631	1308547	1322749	1188007	1280947	344497	1023277	577807	463807	1855237	692539	1020583	1915099	699961	2171497	954067	984667	2040193
827677	897007	729679	562351	631681	932209	1468927	827899	186871	723589	1419697	625237	882907	1140577	346117	852253	354799	1189453	2024107	1526653	445447	183247	1370077	2556907	2294707
107647	571789	878131	739117	1351711	791929	347251	1148167	988279	863869	1284007	742537	1421317	484867	481807	19447	1358323	1686367	523669	2359459	776683	1755487	1786087	568657	1963471
1259527	990259	484609	498859	415141	1065667	1327009	416071	691591	639157	218137	609067	679207	1446997	1461127	2254129	667753	1866859	1137247	21277	2692297	708583	728971	2216377	504157

It is **block-structured prime magic square** of order 25. It is composed of **different sums** prime magic squares of order 5. The internal blocks of order 3 are also **different sums** prime magic squares of order 3. In this case the magic square sum is

$$S_{25 \times 25} := 25000075$$

Example 12. Equal Sums Blocks of Order 5 Let's consider a following prime magic square of order 25:

452983	1820773	1914769	778507	32983	733123	138739	1137229	1992307	998617	1371943	1779829	960937	554209	333097	554677	1649419	1260283	1484419	51217	1750153	656263	74077	990523	1528999
1685773	1197649	95287	1707073	314233	1561597	1010167	1971349	18493	438409	538303	1284763	914239	801007	1461703	708223	522919	1715107	761983	1291783	123757	1083073	930499	986437	1876249
15607	1509427	1000003	490579	1984399	662743	8329	1000003	1991677	1337263	126913	516247	1000003	1483759	1873093	635389	1239067	1000003	760939	1364617	1474549	903367	1000003	1096639	525457
878629	292933	1904719	802357	1121377	1041163	1981513	28657	989839	958843	1295947	1198999	1085767	715243	704059	1152937	1238023	284899	1477087	847069	1180549	1013569	1069507	916933	819457
1967023	179233	85237	1221499	1547023	1001389	1861267	862777	7699	1266883	1666909	220177	1039069	1445797	628063	1948789	350587	739723	515587	1445329	471007	1343743	1925929	1009483	249853
1306633	1572217	1668847	334099	118219	925087	1221289	817987	1008979	1026673	632053	263737	1843273	1516639	744313	1269343	1583287	360307	1276039	511039	324949	1789519	824497	1630597	430453
248407	1627033	481417	891559	1751599	937639	733519	1303987	962503	1062367	30307	631537	1167289	1201183	1969699	731719	1097743	1725379	176887	1268287	841327	769003	1960789	270217	1158679
149749	264529	1000003	1735477	1850257	883483	1228987	1000003	771019	1116523	1084459	1569649	1000003	430357	915547	1155823	79147	1000003	1920859	844183	444187	501217	1000003	1498789	1555819
1413439	1108447	1518589	372973	586567	1280473	1037503	696019	1266487	719533	1997503	798823	832717	1368469	2503	354163	1823119	274627	902263	1645843	1819999	1729789	39217	1231003	180007
1881787	427789	331159	1665907	693373	973333	778717	1182019	991027	1074919	1255693	1736269	156733	483367	1367953	1488967	416719	1639699	723967	730663	1569553	210487	1175509	369409	1675057
4027	1990123	1701313	321319	983233	403339	1642423	841333	1571377	541543	958183	1788217	357727	226669	1669219	1646377	1506979	640069	468703	737887	1263307	1518799	703663	4783	1509463
1071739	894403	1988653	116953	928267	1368547	1351243	176179	1472587	631459	1296649	631993	1524337	843679	703357	325447	1216987	599899	1183123	1674559	1150783	1410553	250057	1339399	849223
1735369	222553	1000003	1777453	264637	1467337	1121347	1000003	878659	532669	589717	1211689	1000003	788317	1410289	873043	966139	1000003	1033867	1126963	1204279	928849	1000003	1071157	795727
1172107	1883053	11353	1105603	827899	302329	527419	1823827	648763	1697677	1824679	1156327	475669	1368013	175327	893029	816883	1400107	783019	1106977	891103	660607	1749949	589453	1108903
1016773	9883	298693	1678687	1995979	1458463	357583	1158673	428629	1596667	330787	211789	1642279	1773337	1041823	1262119	493027	1359937	1531303	353629	490543	481207	1296343	1995223	736699
304849	656329	703819	1987099	1347919	858433	766687	577069	1381027	1416799	1355449	94723	1829197	590599	1130047	513673	255457	1999219	1911103	320563	1456123	1350823	1230949	54277	907843
1254013	767707	1320199	912103	745993	1902319	605323	806263	1588423	97687	614827	377257	1682179	940573	1385179	852763	1613959	101467	1284583	1147243	789829	947803	1222219	829987	1210177
1004677	1144399	1000003	855607	995329	149827	1983103	1000003	16903	1850179	1517107	1563319	1000003	436687	482899	194647	670627	1000003	1329379	1805359	672073	882187	1000003	1117819	1327933
1784389	1087903	679807	1232299	215617	1506229	411583	1193743	1394683	493777	642673	1059433	317827	1622749	1357333	1759489	715423	1898539	386047	240517	989827	1170019	777787	1052203	1010179
652087	1343677	1296187	12907	1695157	583207	1233319	1422937	618979	1141573	869959	1905283	170809	1409407	644557	1679443	1744549	787	88903	1486333	1092163	649183	769057	1945729	543883
1811443	324889	528883	434437	1900363	1461913	1426519	763423	545863	802297	1230667	115399	1868059	859093	926797	3463	1664557	1165303	1998679	168013	520447	1702549	1650157	1024663	102199
1528333	571303	1334329	1094377	471673	1177489	308137	1385389	1306483	822517	628093	1520509	79537	1399963	1371913	10453	1168639	1330957	500413	1989553	652189	749083	508909	1742017	1347817
1245067	1523077	1000003	476929	754939	242227	1998349	1000003	1657	1757779	1407019	879457	1000003	1120549	592987	1473247	331777	1000003	1668229	526759	1571839	1992937	1000003	7069	428167
315529	905629	665677	1428703	1684477	920677	693523	614617	1691869	1079329	661027	600043	1920469	479497	1338979	1680859	1499593	669049	831367	319147	357733	257989	1491097	1250923	1642273
99643	1675117	1471123	1565569	188563	1197709	573487	1236583	1454143	538093	1073209	1884607	131947	1140913	769339	1831993	335449	834703	1327	1996543	1897807	297457	349849	975343	1479559

It is **block-structured prime magic square** of order 25. It is composed of **equal sums** prime magic squares of order 5. The internal blocks of order 3 are also of **equal sums** prime magic squares of order 3. In this case the magic squares sums are

$$S_{25 \times 25} := 25000075, S_{5 \times 5} := 5000015 \text{ and } S_{3 \times 3} := 3000009$$

Example 13. Single-Layer Bordered Prime Magic Square Let's consider a following prime magic square of order 25:

17419	434683	552793	981049	80329	699367	706267	602947	459223	941023	552379	723103	651943	395449	581767	1954717	1898077	468109	1844923	1995583	1998397	1995073	1997119	1996279	472057
486589	1865329	479023	65629	547453	373669	768409	556609	791317	764587	878167	455599	614179	154423	522787	1870717	1828243	1907527	1572679	1895263	1627237	1777717	1675579	7927	1513417
312349	689869	1373473	611953	526087	568207	942013	411127	203947	643243	550489	215617	218437	156823	898753	1674559	1717567	1831447	1978507	1993039	1979683	1988263	516829	1310137	1687657
997897	867079	69067	255349	811729	66883	441523	576553	286513	869203	994579	848227	154873	997933	991777	902137	1684489	1749229	1975627	1999273	1995913	1398247	1930939	1132927	1002109
36007	970069	308587	889489	721207	584359	356509	920677	774853	423127	86287	516883	331693	131749	1795327	1889527	1966663	1912213	1998019	1998349	592609	1110517	1691419	1029937	1963999
19759	664549	265813	259783	868867	1859323	208213	509653	164413	830419	1627	272719	111409	1953517	1640077	1421689	1997503	1998679	1999867	30937	1131139	1740223	1734193	1335457	1980247
510613	556279	511963	195457	726589	746659	2953	63607	611587	519433	734887	327343	769807	215983	1890103	1978993	1997467	1971127	1916749	1253347	1273417	1804549	1488043	1443727	1489393
105667	924727	385249	638263	734653	556849	230143	721843	501463	310789	4219	860323	906679	603283	1992637	1998943	1934887	1164967	1769863	1443157	1265353	1361743	1614757	1075279	1894339
791797	342379	325219	453949	556537	598789	536059	754903	812167	586129	816037	972319	614527	579907	1225723	1898539	1494679	1245103	1463947	1401217	1443469	1546057	1674787	1657627	1208209
209263	329143	363757	714487	20773	487897	76873	707467	986113	23893	372277	674299	348259	1985239	1738837	1857217	1013893	1292539	1923133	1512109	1979233	1285519	1636249	1670863	1790743
33199	80713	293467	321367	330607	810427	418357	571069	93889	428797	1996237	569887	517003	1834969	81919	1571209	1906117	1428937	1581649	1189579	1669399	1678639	1706539	1919293	1966807
278233	419803	399613	115663	75703	891559	429277	410953	614893	1873513	567649	999613	1004677	995719	1432357	126493	1385113	1589053	1570729	1108447	1924303	1884343	1600393	1580203	1721773
13249	561559	593059	158449	64927	784219	1968829	357913	427417	1781407	444043	996109	1000003	1003897	1555963	218599	1572589	1642093	31177	1215787	1935079	1841557	1406947	1438447	1986757
24859	365689	580033	882529	883783	756199	1864399	1677037	1834663	1478689	73999	1004287	995329	1000393	1926007	521317	165343	322969	135607	1243807	1116223	1117477	1419973	1634317	1975147
1770547	420367	610843	1798183	888109	714739	1445929	1126537	1934389	1270933	1918087	1430119	1483003	165037	3769	729073	65617	873469	554077	1285267	1111897	201823	1389163	1579639	229459
1922689	518059	1914103	1805887	1803973	724729	1969153	1927963	1791169	142789	1627729	1325707	1651747	14767	261169	1976113	208837	72043	30853	1275277	196033	194119	85903	1481947	77317
1997539	112927	1597873	1945597	1943437	125113	1999567	1909309	505327	1413877	1183969	1027687	1385479	1420099	774283	101467	1187839	90697	439	1874893	56569	54409	402133	1887079	2467
1991443	1879723	1989049	1994227	1993759	1985587	1975243	835039	1498543	1689217	1995787	1139683	1093327	1396723	7369	1063	65119	1278163	24763	14419	6247	5779	10957	120283	8563
1965637	1632637	1980409	1973143	1997293	1988887	83257	1936399	1388419	1480573	1265119	1672663	1230199	1784023	109903	21013	2539	28879	1997053	11119	2713	26863	19597	367369	34369
1990237	1921363	1988689	1999969	1982437	1969069	1791793	1490353	1835593	1169587	1998379	1727287	1888597	46489	359929	578317	2503	1327	139	140683	17569	37	11317	78643	9769
1999297	1945873	1997173	1996507	1407397	1415647	1643497	1079329	1225153	1576879	1913719	1483123	1668313	1868257	204679	110479	33343	87793	1987	1657	1278799	3499	2833	54133	709
1999549	1993477	1969447	601759	1188277	1933123	1558483	1423453	1713493	1130803	1005427	1151779	1845133	1002073	1008229	1097869	315517	250777	24379	733	4093	1744657	30559	6529	457
1999069	1946377	1483177	1388053	1473919	1431799	1057993	1588879	1796059	1356763	1449517	1784389	1781569	1843183	1101253	325447	282439	168559	21499	6967	20323	11743	626533	53629	937
1999219	1992079	1520983	1934377	1452553	1626337	1231597	1443397	1208689	1235419	1121839	1544407	1385827	1845583	1477219	129289	171763	92479	427327	104743	372769	222289	324427	134677	787
1527949	1565323	1447213	1018957	1919677	1300639	1293739	1397059	1540783	1058983	1447627	1276903	1348063	1604557	1418239	45289	101929	1531897	155083	4423	1609	4933	2887	3727	1982587

*It is **concentric single-layer bordered prime magic square** of order 25. The internal prime magic squares of orders 23 is also a **concentric single-layer bordered prime magic square** and is studied by author in previous work [11]. In this case the magic square sum is*

$$S_{25 \times 25} := 25000075$$

3.3 Prime Magic Squares of Order 26

Below are few examples of prime magic squares of order 26 with different representations. It based on the examples of prime magic squares of order 24.

Example 14. Block-Bordered Embedded Prime Magic Square Let's consider a following prime magic square of order 26:

1861759	1093747	1522693	434989	632683	1652773	1592923	1441009	1223977	1220239	817303	1297669	425899	522259	1027207	1410247	1460377	796267	345637	1033693	503653	1546117	678253	542587	759799	156319
1547563	811879	524287	1808761	386143	255679	891907	1152799	744397	2569093	769207	476167	1609717	667333	423463	1449673	327133	213133	738313	1210879	787207	2723353	874597	576889	2008063	452443
1163329	2045191	1048309	51427	1017007	511243	5479	2905057	1488763	72469	1792207	951697	111187	1629163	846823	64483	837373	426193	15013	3086287	1573813	61339	2286649	1153183	19717	836677
778759	287857	1572331	1284739	130579	766807	636343	408433	2233129	1824727	293677	1427227	1134187	243973	1270183	1026313	114073	639253	525253	424273	2360419	1936747	298303	1729477	1431769	1221247
1105339	819937	511447	1737007	971077	606313	2060161	610447	393961	1358059	764611	488617	1678399	691813	454513	1580533	597679	393109	1367539	961141	607093	2073457	912403	545773	1814983	894667
393853	1939867	1022797	105727	2301601	1212517	123433	1535101	787489	39877	1890997	977209	63421	1797673	908953	20233	1555969	786109	16249	2326213	1213897	101581	1993633	1091053	188473	1606153
347287	308587	1534147	1225657	364873	1818721	1453957	216919	1181017	964531	276019	1465801	1189807	237373	1363393	1126093	204679	1179109	974539	354337	1820701	1466653	367123	1636333	1269703	1652719
664597	1062349	596599	1919689	1174099	762499	2637799	375757	237607	812257	657313	403861	1360207	1206181	764293	2614237	687823	458629	1604347	872863	541543	1834813	365509	235891	813907	1335409
1059103	2050219	1192879	335539	2988499	1524799	61099	911707	475207	38707	1510021	807127	104233	2936293	1528237	120181	1833457	916933	409	2045023	1083073	121123	920167	471769	23371	940903
758743	466069	1789159	1323409	411799	2287099	1875499	138157	712807	574657	254047	1210393	956941	442237	2292181	1850293	229519	1375237	1146043	331333	1624603	1293283	129631	707647	578029	1241263
1516363	686947	368197	1152937	602233	376009	1276117	959953	624517	2161189	959779	632089	2200069	567319	358867	1221811	1426237	935461	3250633	103669	64717	219301	994711	642133	2215177	483643
1191643	1202017	736027	270037	1425337	751453	77569	2449789	1248553	47317	2504269	1263979	23689	1370491	715999	61507	3695173	1870777	46381	244861	129229	13597	2504473	1284007	63541	808363
1652947	319117	1103857	785107	226789	1126897	900673	335917	1872589	1537153	327889	1895869	1568179	210187	1073131	864679	490921	2806093	2315317	39157	193741	154789	352837	1925881	1573303	347059
509563	790927	502501	1720909	415153	205603	612823	1233763	794407	2738269	887017	497671	1600993	530227	338893	1163821	585073	335893	1093633	1011343	664273	2309803	1065109	661417	2240551	1490443
1246579	1934761	1004779	74797	608863	411193	213523	3093319	1588813	84307	1709203	995227	281251	1311241	677647	44053	1180093	671533	162973	2626933	1328473	30013	2497801	1322359	146917	753427
301753	288649	1507057	1218631	209563	616783	407233	439357	2383219	1943863	389461	1492783	1103437	191473	1016401	825067	249433	1007173	757993	347143	1992673	1645603	404167	1983301	1579609	1698253
661183	498523	313477	1068499	866083	505459	1659877	847543	495043	1626013	1043683	686773	2389063	1087027	689257	2358877	778699	485977	1650031	784627	514357	1786327	511939	310819	1042099	1338823
1120087	1196809	626833	56857	1804267	1010473	216679	1768003	989533	211063	2718553	1373173	27793	2650237	1378387	106537	1842901	971569	100237	2030137	1028437	26737	1151779	621619	91459	879919
1623367	185167	940189	755143	361069	1515487	1154863	353053	1484023	1131523	357283	2059573	1702663	397897	2067517	1669747	293107	1457161	1164439	270547	1542517	1272247	201139	932419	731299	376639
1419589	926467	609277	2119717	663541	432907	1499569	903457	567367	1933177	600169	390781	1353607	1442899	691231	2013127	846751	544123	1872097	736249	456349	1544449	463537	308923	1080301	580417
518059	2411737	1218487	25237	1701367	865339	29311	2164387	1134667	104947	1534957	781519	28081	1952647	1382419	812191	2113003	1087657	62311	1720549	912349	104149	1234351	617587	823	1481947
381673	317257	1827697	1510507	231109	1297771	1067137	336157	1701967	1365877	209431	1172257	962869	751711	2073607	1321939	303217	1631191	1328563	280249	1368349	1088449	154873	926251	771637	1618333
936967	862447	574969	2012323	1288891	856693	2993437	290419	143719	426859	670303	425197	1454779	422479	280909	981289	959209	634717	2213833	562519	365527	1264213	1084777	719227	2511337	1063039
654499	2299789	1149913	37	3417553	1713007	8461	423439	286999	150559	1634569	850093	65617	1120369	561559	2749	2523877	1269253	14629	1432447	730753	29059	2865007	1438447	11887	1345507
741787	287503	1724857	1437379	432577	2569321	2137123	147139	430279	283579	245407	1274989	1029883	141829	842209	700639	324673	1903789	1579297	197293	1095979	898987	365557	2157667	1792117	1258219
1843687	906259	477313	1565017	1367323	347233	407083	558997	776029	779767	1182703	702337	1574107	1477747	972799	589759	539629	1203739	1654369	966313	1496353	453889	1321753	1457419	1240207	138247

It is **block-bordered prime magic square** of order 26 embedded with four equal sums prime magic squares of order 12. Each block of order 12 is composed of 16 **different sums** prime magic squares of order 3. In this case the magic squares sums are

$$S_{26 \times 26} := 26000078 \quad S_{24 \times 24} := 24000072 \quad \text{and} \quad S_{12 \times 12} := 12000036$$

Example 15. Block-Bordered Embedded Prime Magic Square Let's consider a following prime magic square of order 26:

326479	603913	566947	1345699	1135333	1005637	947299	1914007	1725859	1532107	1291603	323137	534049	85297	915283	399937	461803	1241869	1115029	334183	1762963	1928947	483367	1488379	898813	1632139
703819	869983	857737	1272289	1376899	311677	1311433	1465993	802297	731719	991777	1978219	30013	758617	1532449	708943	854713	644653	1500643	570373	1167847	1261789	576379	1867147	556483	1296187
1699039	1402309	1000003	597697	934537	1000003	1065469	265729	1000003	1734277	38239	1000003	1961767	950329	1000003	1049677	1645933	1000003	354073	1691419	1000003	308587	980107	1000003	1019899	300967
518017	727717	1142269	1130023	688573	1688329	623107	1268287	1197709	534013	1969993	21787	1008229	1291063	467557	1241389	499363	1355353	1145293	738217	832159	1429633	1443523	132859	1423627	1481989
564643	136777	1736269	1126963	674833	1637773	687403	848839	661777	1489393	1718083	208213	1073713	1046413	832339	1121257	978883	819187	1201939	556609	997897	1445503	989803	652453	1357753	1435363
294103	1990189	1000003	9817	1012573	1000003	987433	1640557	1000003	359449	355633	1000003	1644373	1074847	1000003	925159	1223059	1000003	776947	1888897	1000003	111109	1367953	1000003	632053	1705903
1011553	873043	263737	1863229	1312603	362233	1325173	510613	1338229	1151167	926293	1791793	281923	878749	1167667	953593	798067	1180819	1021123	554503	1002109	1443397	642253	1347553	1010203	988453
1124377	1072957	404119	1522933	1094089	12697	1893223	474583	1118599	1406827	932983	142057	1924969	1030957	1776499	192553	1055233	1013239	931537	1324033	1166413	509563	1728409	44617	1226983	875629
1645543	1449979	1000003	550027	1799137	1000003	200869	1932247	1000003	67759	1991989	1000003	8017	161599	1000003	1838407	876307	1000003	1123699	185533	1000003	1814473	498577	1000003	1501429	354463
1605757	477073	1595887	927049	106783	1987309	905917	593179	881407	1525423	75037	1857949	1067023	1807453	223507	969049	1068469	986767	944773	1490443	833593	675973	773023	1955389	271597	394249
1574563	1845133	49117	1105759	723259	965197	1311553	693733	848593	1457683	650599	1238197	1111213	1937323	41299	1021387	942889	421987	1635133	434989	1639357	925663	1136719	1437097	426193	425443
58699	260629	1000003	1739377	1588297	1000003	411709	1763953	1000003	236053	1460617	1000003	539389	84067	1000003	1915939	1692247	1000003	307759	1490677	1000003	509329	289477	1000003	1710529	1941307
1082377	894247	1950889	154873	688453	1034809	1276747	542323	1151413	1306273	888793	761809	1349407	978619	1958707	62683	364873	1578019	1057117	1074343	360649	1565017	1573813	562909	863287	917629
618799	1330873	945409	723727	1523407	848959	627643	626323	1524637	849049	1317853	721219	960937	1042597	963709	993703	1438303	815047	746659	820273	627139	1552597	1177453	902347	920209	1381207
55009	392857	1000003	1607149	104239	1000003	1895767	1222729	1000003	777277	643087	1000003	1356919	951109	1000003	1048897	308359	1000003	1691647	1732327	1000003	267679	742759	1000003	1257247	1944997
1617277	1276279	1054597	669133	1372363	1151047	476599	1150957	475369	1373683	1039069	1278787	682153	1006303	1036297	957409	1253347	1184959	561703	447409	1372867	1179733	1079797	1097659	822553	382729
1642273	662443	847009	1490557	893413	1091047	1015549	930199	1992937	76873	1143013	1323997	532999	478243	1321513	1200253	575647	1278619	1145743	1193503	280243	1526263	603349	1860637	536023	357733
1551619	1828117	1000003	171889	1122139	1000003	877867	146677	1000003	1853329	389989	1000003	1610017	1722013	1000003	277993	1570099	1000003	429907	1332763	1000003	667243	932677	1000003	1067329	448387
872563	509449	1152997	1337563	984457	908959	1106593	1923133	7069	1069807	1467007	676009	856993	799753	678493	1521763	854263	721387	1424359	473743	1719763	806503	1463983	139369	1396657	1127443
160879	499033	1239013	1261963	1060519	196927	1742563	1329703	1252729	417577	630613	1645537	723859	790033	1521193	688783	381673	1836979	781357	1054429	69127	1876453	885097	1863559	251353	1839127
1841779	1762933	1000003	237073	1682047	1000003	317959	87877	1000003	1912129	1093249	1000003	906757	898753	1000003	1101253	1399687	1000003	600319	1822027	1000003	177979	366259	1000003	1633747	158227
1799983	738043	760993	1500973	257443	1803079	939487	1582429	747277	670303	1276147	354469	1369393	1311223	478813	1209973	1218649	163027	1618333	123553	1930879	945577	1748653	136447	1114909	200023
1847767	1930603	3457	1065949	1460377	1041109	498523	1002553	1876009	121447	933313	1857967	208729	718813	620623	1660573	860383	295129	1844497	1820977	172519	1006513	239803	1780027	980179	152239
696937	135349	1000003	1864657	38149	1000003	1961857	118897	1000003	1881109	275419	1000003	1724587	1941763	1000003	58243	1984117	1000003	15889	185539	1000003	1814467	1740379	1000003	259627	1303069
718357	934057	1996549	69403	1501483	958897	539629	1878559	123997	997453	1791277	142039	1066693	339433	1379383	1281193	155509	1704877	1139623	993493	1827487	179029	1019827	219979	1760203	1281649
367867	1396093	1433059	654307	864673	994369	1052707	85999	274147	467899	708403	1676869	1465957	1914709	1084723	1600069	1538203	758137	884977	1665823	237043	71059	1516639	511627	1101193	1673527

It is **block-bordered prime magic square** of order 26 embedded with prime magic square of order 24. The prime magic square of order 24 is composed **equal sums** prime magic squares of order 3. In order to bring these magic squares of order 3 to become equal sums a repeated prime number 100003 is considered in middle of each block of order 3. In this case the magic squares sums are

$$S_{26 \times 26} := 26000078 \quad S_{24 \times 24} := 24000072 \quad \text{and} \quad S_{3 \times 3} := 3000009$$

Example 16. Block-Bordered Embedded Prime Magic Square Let's consider a following prime magic square of order 26:

943837	700087	662743	372769	1411603	1652947	1197073	806857	570373	1490317	539233	385597	1529797	967363	1228327	479497	1520689	1643269	1173043	1343197	336529	421453	453367	1608133	1582429	979549
1385113	907759	1051417	757909	901567	556093	1232713	474241	1150861	574657	1659919	823819	1909081	1801489	1431733	1547773	1178017	788383	644089	567097	422803	1336333	1159843	649483	472993	614893
364423	1120237	626623	1182703	689089	1255021	1099741	607213	451933	1867231	958021	1525717	616507	1080913	1767307	1212199	1898593	402817	933703	277483	808369	591709	412387	1396939	1217617	1635583
1186099	378733	322459	1486867	1430593	868561	921601	785353	838393	1545769	552859	1930879	937969	1720867	2213053	766453	1258639	289669	780583	430603	921517	1389163	1447273	362053	420163	813907
970063	1211923	1618153	191173	597403	734233	159853	1547101	972721	979819	1796677	687061	1503919	1355743	546919	2432587	1623763	941503	63997	1147189	269683	301447	599149	1210177	1507879	1029943
517999	1289557	952507	1721911	1384861	1099723	1445047	554959	900283	486667	564667	760927	838927	360457	190339	639487	469369	1343029	858883	1141123	656977	1342093	1897807	1272379	1828093	1482007
1581649	1533331	889081	1785337	1141087	431863	1265053	734953	1568143	804091	911227	414367	521503	293599	657583	172243	536227	829987	711577	1288429	1170019	1938829	721213	2448973	1231357	418357
1600069	1353487	1006177	1668241	1320931	1066063	962413	1037593	933943	1026457	1063921	261673	299137	350899	363343	466483	478927	928099	1155709	844297	1071907	2138377	1142233	2027953	1031809	399937
703327	1172461	2501071	173347	1501957	1402363	327499	1672507	597643	333973	111373	1214221	991621	654697	448387	381439	175129	898897	1273843	726163	1101109	921073	2579119	591067	2249113	1296679
1281649	978157	1172257	344017	538117	1530691	840571	1452487	762367	863299	998917	1191769	1327387	1081687	541237	1649449	1108999	672883	1800529	988297	2115943	385537	271867	748639	634969	718357
1449829	339673	968911	547363	1176601	945577	1154017	1139041	1347481	1418797	1508449	682237	771889	1351069	880723	1309963	839617	1585219	1748407	1040419	1203607	665479	797593	222913	355027	550177
728209	560317	792667	723607	955957	1195021	1769881	523177	1098037	1024357	1296829	893857	1166329	1298719	1312513	878173	891967	1951153	1052893	1735933	837673	255499	448633	571873	765007	1271797
1394413	1154401	98713	1417561	361873	914827	821647	1471411	1378231	1074919	577177	1613509	1115767	649897	1646899	543787	1540789	1368397	975823	1813003	1420429	734497	522919	497587	286009	605593
713737	1347001	653893	2132941	1439833	857569	779899	421159	343489	1123699	1352557	659569	888427	1114039	1686403	510943	1083307	166783	249763	528691	611671	2062759	980149	2044069	961459	1286269
1532173	1190851	2097763	689071	1595983	883357	516709	684349	317701	1062367	818383	1193743	949759	668677	1006237	1191109	1528669	419191	527701	250753	359263	907891	1256149	1768069	2116327	467833
383107	1635163	2044111	742723	1151671	389161	1102249	98809	811897	1007047	1110943	901183	1005079	1025509	533809	1663537	1171837	334603	58153	720301	443851	2371627	2612749	411469	652591	1616899
753547	1400653	777901	2008933	1386181	272029	3259	1197799	929029	831139	742369	1269757	1180987	1586467	1168243	1029103	610879	636331	721291	57163	142123	706159	1199389	1824829	2318059	1246459
497047	640531	583087	642211	584767	1241557	670333	1329673	758449	1692697	1160953	1613761	1082017	740527	1413877	1413001	2086351	1177243	473419	1526587	822763	545497	838963	334171	627637	1502959
1458427	520309	310927	914371	704989	1380727	931789	1068217	619279	896263	1955251	819463	1878451	1946809	1604821	1222057	880069	1058839	1369393	630613	941167	796981	443761	729373	376153	541579
1012399	946489	608191	617107	278809	727459	1523077	476929	1272547	653281	1340761	1433953	2121433	934051	312979	2513899	1892827	1046827	1829533	170473	953179	903493	888961	284173	269641	987607
603913	343267	948391	276907	882031	650269	874813	1125193	1349737	2307187	1092463	1682251	467527	2032369	2322079	504799	794509	717103	327667	1672339	1282903	100297	174583	998551	1072837	1396093
1396453	1356499	666403	1321483	631387	568903	1245781	1553173	2230051	413089	951109	262069	800089	438133	458323	517471	537661	1948927	914467	2307091	1272631	1002523	525529	1277137	800143	603553
677119	711847	1447807	540079	1276039	1398367	2112007	686947	1400587	618439	356869	856309	594739	645481	464617	511177	330313	977671	1556551	1665007	2243887	637669	551917	1250749	1164997	1322887
1183123	835489	1732369	255517	1152397	1480771	531043	2267911	1318183	969757	344887	868291	243421	675601	710377	265417	300193	1190149	1179109	2042449	2031409	1366693	955993	846673	435973	816883
661897	1071937	129193	1858693	915949	2149867	1709077	1089877	649087	425071	773491	439687	788107	192373	318271	657523	783421	2326369	2792989	428569	895189	598447	1571893	230773	1204219	1338109
1020457	1299919	1337263	1627237	588403	347059	802933	1193149	1429633	509689	1460773	1614409	470209	1032643	771679	1520509	479317	356737	826963	656809	1663477	1578553	1546639	391873	417577	1056169

It is **block-bordered prime magic square** of order 26 embedded with four equal sums prime magic squares of order 12. Each block of order 12 is composed of 9 **different sums** prime magic squares of order 4. In this case the magic squares sums are

$$S_{26 \times 26} := 26000078, S_{24 \times 24} := 24000072 \text{ and } S_{12 \times 12} := 12000036$$

Example 17. Block-Bordered Embedded Prime Magic Square Let's consider a following prime magic square of order 26:

326479	603913	566947	1345699	1135333	1005637	947299	1914007	1725859	1532107	1291603	323137	534049	85297	915283	399937	461803	1241869	1115029	334183	1762963	1928947	483367	1488379	898813	1632139
703819	1688179	307669	1692337	311827	1693303	309223	1690783	306703	1695283	310729	1689277	304723	1698013	308317	1691689	301993	1130953	873469	1126537	869053	1131553	869983	1130023	868453	1296187
1699039	315517	1998397	1609	1684489	313333	1993273	6733	1686673	314239	1991293	8713	1685767	312709	1988563	11443	1687297	873913	1994827	5179	1126093	875803	1994227	5779	1124203	300967
518017	733	1690993	309013	1999273	439	1693639	306367	1999567	457	1696543	303463	1999549	1063	1698349	301657	1998943	709	1131343	868663	1999297	139	1133263	866743	1999867	1481989
564643	1995583	2953	1997053	4423	1992937	3877	1996129	7069	1990033	1447	1998559	9973	1988227	4783	1995223	11779	1994437	373	1999633	5569	1992517	2539	1997467	7489	1435363
294103	1294123	706633	1293373	705883	1299583	706267	1293739	700423	1306519	710293	1289713	693487	1344199	652237	1347769	655807	1358779	645937	1354069	641227	1387129	651517	1348489	612877	1705903
1011553	710257	1994479	5527	1289749	707467	1989019	10987	1292539	695917	1982083	17923	1304089	659047	1996459	3547	1340959	660277	1981879	18127	1339729	635287	1953529	46477	1364719	988453
1124377	3643	1296613	703393	1996363	4993	1300633	699373	1995013	15823	1306849	693157	1984183	1987	1345879	654127	1998019	37	1359739	640267	1999969	26497	1389559	610447	1973509	875629
1645543	1991989	2287	1997719	8017	1987969	4093	1995913	12037	1981753	787	1999219	18253	1994779	5437	1994569	5227	1980919	12457	1987549	19087	1951099	5407	1994599	48907	354463
1605757	1174759	836449	1163557	825247	1113877	893029	1106977	886129	1125127	897469	1102537	874879	1130047	890119	1109887	869959	1153777	875209	1124797	846229	1500643	517243	1482763	499363	394249
1574563	831367	1977817	22189	1168639	906649	1974787	25219	1093357	905449	1963537	36469	1094557	904759	1958617	41389	1095247	905959	1934887	65119	1094047	504943	1976239	23767	1495063	425443
58699	19483	1178173	821833	1980523	14629	1123807	876199	1985377	10729	1129957	870049	1989277	19609	1143067	856939	1980397	19249	1167637	832369	1980757	19777	1502233	497773	1980229	1941307
1082377	1974403	7573	1992433	25603	1964857	8389	1991617	35149	1958707	9049	1990957	41299	1945597	8209	1991797	54409	1921027	22279	1977727	78979	1974649	4297	1995709	25357	917629
618799	1381459	643969	1356037	618547	1018873	987997	1012009	981133	1019449	998443	1001563	980557	1032679	983407	1016599	967327	1039069	979423	1020583	960937	1007023	991633	1008373	992983	1381207
55009	626317	1965973	34033	1373689	995227	1726939	273067	1004779	982687	1726363	273643	1017319	983863	1713133	286873	1016143	984457	1706743	293263	1015549	990163	1747087	252919	1009843	1944997
1617277	27337	1382533	617473	1972669	259219	1019119	980887	1740787	277687	1025623	974383	1722319	273997	1036339	963667	1726009	272257	1041583	958423	1727749	260809	1012093	987913	1739197	382729
1642273	1964899	7537	1992469	35107	1726693	265957	1734049	273313	1720189	249583	1750423	279817	1709473	267133	1732873	290533	1704229	272263	1727743	295777	1742017	249199	1750807	257989	357733
1551619	1875859	127453	1872553	124147	1879243	138427	1861579	120763	1538029	435637	1564369	461977	1578289	453367	1546639	421717	1581649	454387	1545619	418357	1590739	429277	1570729	409267	448387
872563	148747	1970407	29599	1851259	150583	1967023	32983	1849423	475927	1974559	25447	1524079	449557	1934299	65707	1550449	432007	1930939	69067	1567999	471607	1921849	78157	1528399	1127443
160879	7459	1878319	121687	1992547	3769	1879849	120157	1996237	29287	1555819	444187	1970719	39217	1579639	420367	1960789	57697	1583929	416077	1942309	19927	1594849	405157	1980079	1839127
1841779	1967947	23833	1976173	32059	1966417	14713	1985293	33589	1956769	33997	1966009	43237	1932949	32707	1967299	67057	1928659	30757	1969249	71347	1917739	54037	1945969	82267	158227
1799983	1032007	982393	1017613	967999	1051153	943429	1056577	948853	1065313	950029	1049977	934693	1404883	622159	1377847	595123	1413283	600469	1399537	586723	1421083	610339	1389667	578923	200023
1847767	962503	1370263	629743	1037503	981577	1351117	648889	1018429	987457	1336957	663049	1012549	611263	1950577	49429	1388743	624199	1942177	57829	1375807	612223	1934377	65629	1387783	152239
696937	650059	1046827	953179	1349947	627379	1062367	937639	1372627	614569	1069597	930409	1385437	35089	1406683	593323	1964917	26317	1419247	580759	1973689	33343	1422097	577909	1966663	1303069
718357	1355443	600529	1399477	644563	1339903	643099	1356907	660103	1332673	643429	1356577	667333	1948777	20593	1979413	51229	1936213	38119	1961887	63793	1933363	33199	1966807	66643	1281649
367867	1396093	1433059	654307	864673	994369	1052707	85999	274147	467899	708403	1676869	1465957	1914709	1084723	1600069	1538203	758137	884977	1665823	237043	71059	1516639	511627	1101193	1673527

It is **block-bordered prime magic square** of order 26 embedded with prime magic square of order 24. The prime magic square of order 24 is composed **equal sums** prime magic squares of order 4. In this case the magic squares sums are

$$S_{26 \times 26} := 26000078, S_{24 \times 24} := 24000072 \text{ and } S_{4 \times 4} := 4000012$$

Example 18. Block-Bordered Embedded Prime Magic Square Let's consider a following prime magic square of order 26:

999907	1194163	539947	1668517	529513	1632307	625939	921199	827293	1719469	299239	1884889	642079	774427	605323	1592923	425977	1049527	1635547	891799	932839	140677	1698253	35569	1733143	999613
968959	1445071	1112047	1597129	411751	1767427	1163689	769309	1754527	1761553	1565269	819457	2549203	755863	696427	154699	605503	379087	189139	414451	738391	874213	1008913	457117	1009837	1031047
1610569	622777	1452439	1038727	1460311	1046599	1876261	1855999	1463587	2126617	946489	1609519	1217107	245989	483643	564463	362443	443263	680917	370477	876373	1111447	389527	624601	1130497	389437
155299	1812091	1140157	1128811	1370227	1358881	686947	2090317	825547	1719049	1354057	2247559	982789	372829	199447	674683	252223	727459	554077	532537	891487	400321	1100653	609487	968437	1844707
1605169	2077849	1933171	2108941	390097	565867	421189	1704763	1868989	1194547	1878559	1204117	1368343	342187	487603	475207	451699	439303	584719	1200253	451837	494443	1006531	1049137	300721	394837
374797	203977	472309	721597	1777441	2026729	2295061	2275027	1988089	1105999	1967107	1085017	798079	326083	683119	139459	787447	243787	600823	1494067	782251	995737	505237	718723	6907	1625209
1793227	1335349	1386991	901909	2087287	731611	1053967	523903	1318579	1311553	1507837	2253649	2303797	737767	230479	772207	321403	547819	171043	491137	762583	626761	492061	1043857	1086523	206779
764623	544837	627901	1273231	1194769	361159	1267897	664711	858877	880687	1162261	346543	1005643	391441	376837	1573699	1269757	1224739	2244841	350851	848593	1315453	1287133	987391	1940821	1235383
272383	1021159	1343767	1390801	365797	412831	735439	965113	609361	1266631	372943	1030213	674461	1863157	699931	1533211	827227	1660507	497281	1819591	862117	908671	1334743	1381297	423823	1727623
1199893	383101	693619	459691	1296907	1062979	1373497	1266301	777313	769273	870301	862261	373273	1788571	1701757	1225657	1134781	658681	571867	1104373	1714441	1343413	900001	528973	1139041	800113
1221427	1200937	474949	802597	954001	1281649	555661	653623	866707	352867	1286707	772867	985951	1997587	500947	107347	2253091	1859491	362851	1098211	637723	932983	1310431	1605691	1145203	778579
1264933	1631059	1000861	860107	896491	755737	125539	735043	1025767	890377	749197	613807	904531	924961	1818241	1854661	505777	542197	1435477	2054623	1272547	1301761	941653	970867	188791	735073
64927	488701	1128697	483367	561829	1395439	1211761	633931	780697	758887	477313	1293031	974863	115597	1983601	786739	1090681	1135699	1968997	302593	1394821	927961	956281	1256023	1892563	1935079
1315537	788167	948847	1055437	380251	917887	826333	1507657	924829	420241	1451059	1358221	437587	1742413	1369561	440227	1108057	1104781	135403	1507879	1692511	894721	528709	1649917	809377	684469
1280173	564097	986941	1256407	382567	652033	1074877	668617	1145371	902389	1130809	887827	1364581	459703	799621	560281	1406533	1167193	1507111	728269	560149	746791	1614247	1800889	1632769	719833
1835329	774853	490993	681253	957721	1147981	864121	1343161	796387	886177	1147021	1236811	690037	921751	1520083	1120153	846661	446731	1045063	1047127	1240081	1779889	581149	1120957	1313911	164677
595069	1198201	624577	492757	1146217	1014397	440773	860791	451621	358531	1674667	1581577	1172407	904693	1025257	1331107	635707	941557	1062121	1645867	1301467	719659	1641379	1059571	715171	1404937
833389	778963	1175437	847531	791443	463537	860011	123757	1673017	1919299	113899	360181	1909441	40471	588667	922087	1044727	1378147	1926343	602311	1620379	1475737	885301	740659	1758727	1166617
247363	812641	690127	583537	1258723	721087	850807	1595611	1108369	1612957	582139	674977	525541	1831411	597253	1526587	858757	862033	224401	1551661	668527	1466317	1832329	711121	853159	1752643
1843999	1254217	1708387	1733827	369133	1027591	223087	148609	977407	504247	210247	944689	977239	456457	1701019	1754419	1372999	618577	2334127	1724551	898069	1169257	1042519	652627	196771	156007
506329	1227547	618463	1190587	914827	1486951	877867	829063	439273	355819	898327	814873	425083	2110519	720289	2129227	616639	2025577	635347	434989	461359	459937	1434661	1433239	1459609	1493677
1594729	1083451	1649887	1065901	1039513	455527	1021963	1025347	466537	820333	433813	787609	228799	2184769	2088907	661099	2084767	656959	561097	605887	1500019	1348309	546289	394579	1288711	405277
276049	356533	1193011	934897	1170517	912403	1748881	339289	772339	429463	824683	481807	914857	1226767	1594297	293149	2452717	1151569	1519099	508789	463921	445771	1448827	1430677	1385809	1723957
1274353	512167	749467	1019443	1085971	1355947	1593247	1143223	830143	902677	351469	424003	110923	1847347	1088239	2408257	337609	1657627	898519	711751	1363897	1535179	359419	530701	1182847	725653
1101253	1882327	397027	371587	1736281	1077823	851197	276907	276739	749899	1043899	309457	1105537	411739	1044847	991447	1372867	2127289	2289409	1697827	996529	725341	852079	1241971	170047	898753
1000393	805843	1460059	331489	1470493	367699	1374067	1078807	1172713	280537	1700767	115117	1357927	1225579	1394683	407083	1574029	950479	364459	1108207	1067167	1859329	301753	1964437	266863	1000099

It is **block-bordered prime magic square** of order 26 embedded with prime magic square of order 24. The prime magic square of order 24 is composed **different sums** concentric magic square of order 6. The internal blocks of order 4 are also prime magic squares with **different magic sums**. In this case the magic squares sums are

$$S_{26 \times 26} := 26000078 \text{ and } S_{24 \times 24} := 24000072$$

Example 19. Block-Bordered Embedded Prime Magic Square Let's consider a following prime magic square of order 26:

581983	824017	354463	427579	986767	1582549	1299583	394249	1620589	1222693	1649287	994093	840943	385597	646873	438937	552379	1480099	1052767	1685599	309469	977209	1599883	1139227	1534327	1418917
1066063	739363	1005643	1069807	1337779	447463	1399963	474499	1479559	1399603	435637	846757	1363963	1420729	1373059	430147	902827	1505899	367357	1928677	1011763	1037497	1023229	453379	545473	933943
326149	1676533	869689	1292539	707467	1130317	323473	1312183	997453	848839	1151167	1002553	687823	1548073	1168039	444349	1555657	831967	451933	1097029	730993	1304503	695503	1269013	902977	1673857
1385383	1322767	1227337	850387	1149619	772669	677239	1049857	1156699	895393	1104613	843307	950149	301747	1364617	1531567	468439	635389	1698259	1173853	971569	592393	1407613	1028437	826153	614623
512467	843379	540577	357667	1642339	1459429	1156627	1605127	454507	501493	1498513	1545499	394879	444877	402763	1635013	364993	1597243	1555129	343423	1530157	556093	1443913	469849	1656583	1487539
1594297	817933	1362409	1499419	500587	637597	1182073	922309	1391353	1754287	245719	608653	1077697	651943	1064593	389083	1610923	935413	1348063	2503	767293	1547023	452983	1232713	1997503	405709
1599253	600043	994363	930199	662227	1552543	1260643	636043	520447	600403	1564369	1153249	1525507	1632649	626947	1569859	1097179	494107	579277	1454533	988243	962509	976777	1546627	71329	400753
1536553	1743283	1093033	1042837	1185469	307339	628057	1172407	1122739	1503529	492403	899917	809023	1238197	1325923	327007	1301929	1280803	526159	278437	628819	1204669	994579	1294087	1599427	463453
324217	1345153	719149	962677	1037329	1280857	654853	1645009	728557	1104373	895633	1271449	354997	1013893	1286617	988417	1011589	713389	986113	1467913	758083	1257493	742513	1241923	532093	1675789
1668757	449563	1548427	671353	1328653	451579	1550443	374839	1061149	1286653	713353	938857	1625167	1664557	1272679	439009	1560997	727327	335449	671323	555523	1145743	854263	1444483	1328683	331249
1109197	730663	1580533	1238599	761407	419473	1269343	388477	1044019	848923	1151083	955987	1611529	438967	1294729	1579639	420367	705277	1561039	1362709	962077	179497	1820509	1037929	637297	890809
1593799	359407	151903	1127383	872623	1848103	1640599	1228303	1166287	760063	1239943	833719	771703	170557	145987	992947	1007059	1854019	1829449	1819057	1724329	1417279	582727	275677	180949	406207
469657	1371949	906973	957169	814537	1692667	256723	1190983	877267	496477	1507603	1100089	827599	1473847	674083	1672999	698077	719203	761809	400579	1371187	795337	1005427	705919	1721569	1530349
1388053	1120513	1348489	770179	357229	1570879	832729	166843	1193869	982453	518017	1431307	1707529	1828423	951109	357583	1062343	1625017	175543	706837	1072957	1461697	444007	1041673	1272847	611953
554833	668623	1139917	851359	1148647	860089	1331383	1380889	885943	1412347	587659	1114063	619117	406507	1092349	1497187	502819	907657	1593499	739027	622603	1483507	516499	1377403	1260979	1445173
630823	1517569	1168249	751579	1248427	831757	482437	1292023	1345879	975313	1024693	654127	707983	336529	463459	1213057	786949	1536547	1663477	858919	1291063	406969	1593037	708943	1141087	1369183
941023	1437019	1169647	1369297	630709	830359	562987	1474843	1280407	1373473	626533	719599	525163	639589	488317	349519	1650487	1511689	1360417	1173043	1521937	465163	1534843	478069	826963	1058983
1135903	89017	522199	1027777	972229	1477807	1910989	1392943	487783	238879	1761127	1512223	607063	964507	1955887	940249	1059757	44119	1035499	1795033	564409	1644373	355633	1435597	204973	864103
649879	1167277	651517	1229827	1642777	429127	879493	292477	806137	1017553	1481989	568699	1833163	1824463	1048897	1642423	937663	374989	171583	727159	927049	538309	1555999	958333	1293169	1350127
1126759	1093357	1360327	970699	1140709	565723	869203	1154353	678649	1415497	323923	1553809	873787	131947	520123	1159303	1198819	1062547	1927279	1395943	356737	1438477	878173	1424869	505819	873247
668509	1147249	1377829	1092907	907099	622177	852757	475159	876607	599407	1400599	1123399	1524847	1694977	1076869	797029	1202977	923137	305029	1211059	1100797	525517	1474489	899209	788947	1331497
1249519	870853	434347	1475323	524683	1565659	1129153	968329	1563319	1182439	817567	436687	1031677	909547	1537897	957823	1042183	462109	1090459	662443	1211629	445699	1554307	788377	1337563	750487
1424749	746203	670693	1336009	663997	1329313	1253803	1397329	1304167	1803127	196879	695839	602677	1530037	1317487	1966933	33073	682519	469969	784153	1396237	1255147	744859	603769	1215853	575257
335047	1011553	1517143	95773	1904233	482863	988453	878629	255919	415039	1584967	1744087	1121377	1660783	67759	278227	1721779	1932247	339223	452233	291349	1773649	226357	1708657	1547773	1664959
1546117	1130803	639679	1029307	859297	1434283	906649	1126219	1321357	584509	1676083	446197	845653	72727	1479883	840703	801187	937459	1868059	1494187	1643269	561529	1121833	575137	604063	453889
581089	1175989	1645543	1572427	1013239	417457	700423	1605757	379417	777313	350719	1005913	1159063	1614409	1353133	1561069	1447627	519907	947239	314407	1690537	1022797	400123	860779	465679	1418023

It is **block-bordered prime magic square** of order 26 embedded with prime magic square of order 24. The prime magic square of order 24 is composed **equal sums** concentric magic square of order 6. The internal blocks of order 4 are also prime magic squares with **equal magic sums**. In this case the magic squares sums are

$$S_{26 \times 26} := 26000078 \quad S_{24 \times 24} := 24000072 \quad S_{6 \times 6} := 6000018 \quad \text{and} \quad S_{4 \times 4} := 4000012.$$

Example 20. Block-Bordered Embedded Prime Magic Square Let's consider a following prime magic square of order 26:

1777807	1115839	666229	1067329	1405309	536233	1094809	907363	476713	1048063	1185463	302287	925399	637657	872023	881233	1650823	1401217	1474069	471769	966139	1494373	1258723	1660063	508909	214237
607627	219217	1409407	1611763	1761169	1814809	467899	2154907	2885173	404011	341491	633307	157639	674161	336361	502651	398611	1635163	326947	1662943	1716181	665221	1067047	549391	604603	1392379
357559	2371423	2193973	517729	1871923	1262887	2407003	989743	709663	356731	802651	569617	338707	592357	248461	34381	505327	618637	359767	1375111	386041	688063	1446007	1915633	1438237	1642447
774073	2365309	2206819	1968979	1948483	1132603	1112107	874267	715777	325747	303937	481417	566149	295909	380641	558121	536311	310111	1112143	1154737	1227151	829723	902137	944731	1746763	1225933
878107	794203	1003957	1667599	1569817	1511269	1413487	2077129	2286883	169129	140839	214141	546961	315097	647917	721219	692929	769033	1046257	1287067	1150057	906817	769807	1010617	1287841	1121899
589903	2069737	717139	736927	1750129	1330957	2344159	2363947	1011349	712429	407899	280717	280537	581521	581341	454159	149629	1576921	1689343	1026043	1658893	397981	1030831	367531	479953	1410103
832339	2110183	1030027	1788667	893743	2187343	1292419	2051059	970903	605497	103171	747841	330469	531589	114217	758887	256561	1712287	1821871	645901	77647	1979227	1410973	235003	344587	1167667
1500823	2198359	2091343	2563357	1209163	1818199	674083	887113	882727	411241	827677	292441	523351	269701	613597	59407	450817	153073	141241	681763	1670833	1368811	610867	1697107	1903801	499183
1451743	195913	1671679	1469323	1319917	1266277	2613187	926179	2861869	463447	520567	228751	704419	187897	525697	359407	458047	1452271	1729927	393931	340693	1391653	989827	1507483	421711	548263
1010683	953221	699073	424843	265471	373987	524743	660097	1741	645019	1516609	801337	1463563	1537513	300967	490579	1244437	2083297	681781	1094161	2052697	1556977	1278379	2325181	1024399	989323
795727	454213	733921	413863	673573	290041	672103	143881	521581	1216393	1054717	1358047	356197	988417	1544563	698077	783613	990349	2378119	1128931	2079787	486091	2063059	936667	2033869	1204279
302173	259213	147727	446323	588481	387313	529471	828067	716581	1229827	624277	1041583	846739	1153267	958423	1375729	770179	511171	485347	2339929	743851	2280367	684289	2538871	2513047	1697833
493777	336247	448387	556327	622927	352867	419467	527407	639547	1573813	1234777	1394893	642673	1357333	605113	765229	426193	2078431	567811	1226011	698977	2325241	1798207	2456407	945787	1506229
1308313	712837	596977	303571	423883	551911	672223	378817	262957	1039513	553369	407083	527803	1472203	1592923	1446637	960493	1742101	2245459	1396237	1952647	1071571	1627981	778759	1282117	691693
855727	171481	168457	645367	316297	659497	330427	807337	804313	1433353	1230949	1156453	1982797	17209	843553	769057	566653	1585447	1308367	1086259	2652961	371257	1937959	1715851	1438771	1144279
1519153	41911	831913	561931	302221	685753	303691	241873	933883	106537	1301929	641959	1643809	1011589	455443	945289	1893469	1106257	2087551	1895287	944431	2538127	961159	646099	1917961	480853
1077673	974053	276721	550951	710323	601807	451051	315697	22573	755569	483397	1198669	536443	462493	1699039	1509427	1354987	1999819	2342437	1930057	971521	1467241	1745839	699037	940921	922333
635989	828547	933931	1592761	336157	838897	852889	1378081	1011289	1298191	632323	1394293	2438587	1834321	1992673	1166227	1795201	482569	653593	332803	461317	186157	688783	414199	456283	1364017
718813	1064131	309577	874831	1516651	1219279	371179	1537897	879007	597613	1394671	2295793	1948327	823177	1425337	1526557	2540341	423289	307339	565483	512137	540187	236329	595303	495637	1281193
1166617	1223941	1265101	1117177	490891	1452247	825961	678037	719197	2537323	1521103	2201827	980503	2157451	936127	1616851	600631	728173	487447	429397	406993	511933	489529	431479	190753	833389
959887	1161169	1047979	1089469	1093129	850009	853669	895159	781969	2634301	756433	2045647	1310371	1827583	1092307	2381521	503653	501133	695089	539509	289243	629683	379417	223837	417793	1040119
956713	1136869	1581487	458791	989467	953671	1484347	361651	806269	2531233	2314231	1161163	2644927	493027	1976791	823723	606721	289417	546097	696373	546067	372859	222553	372829	629509	1043293
1533937	315067	1220029	1220839	1312789	630349	722299	723109	1628071	1610251	1816027	867271	1340107	1797847	2270683	1321927	1527703	547537	397183	172573	595549	323377	746353	521743	371389	466069
620647	1110979	405241	1068307	426487	723859	1571959	1633561	832159	151	1611397	842161	1189627	2314777	1712617	1743283	3137803	240943	323623	353443	406789	378739	682597	611587	677983	1379359
1488499	931849	1009207	350377	1606981	1104241	1090249	565057	1114591	1342753	2505631	1743661	699367	1303633	1145281	1971727	1839763	462643	265333	586123	457609	732769	230143	504727	436357	511507
1785769	884167	1333777	932677	594697	1463773	905197	1092643	1523293	951943	814543	1697719	1074607	1362349	1127983	1118773	349183	598789	525937	1528237	1033867	505633	741283	339943	1491097	222199

It is **block-bordered prime magic square** of order 26 embedded with prime magic square of order 24. It is composed of **different sums concentric prime magic square** of order 8. The internal blocks of orders 6 and 4 are also of **different sums prime magic squares**. In this case the magic squares sums are

$$S_{26 \times 26} := 26000078 \text{ and } S_{24 \times 24} := 24000072$$

Example 21. Block-Bordered Embedded Prime Magic Square Let's consider a following prime magic square of order 26:

1777807	1115839	666229	1067329	1405309	536233	1094809	907363	476713	1048063	1185463	302287	925399	637657	872023	881233	1650823	1401217	1474069	471769	966139	1494373	1258723	1660063	508909	214237
607627	1595557	468859	1993759	1514179	120577	447463	813217	1046413	1595557	468859	1993759	1514179	120577	447463	813217	1046413	1595557	468859	1993759	1514179	120577	447463	813217	1046413	1392379
357559	799063	1518709	114487	1896043	588433	1864417	17929	1200943	799063	1518709	114487	1896043	588433	1864417	17929	1200943	799063	1518709	114487	1896043	588433	1864417	17929	1200943	1642447
774073	1230379	1573813	1033567	954043	1045963	966439	426193	769627	1230379	1573813	1033567	954043	1045963	966439	426193	769627	1230379	1573813	1033567	954043	1045963	966439	426193	769627	1225933
878107	1476913	264529	1570099	1244029	755977	429907	1735477	523093	1476913	264529	1570099	1244029	755977	429907	1735477	523093	1476913	264529	1570099	1244029	755977	429907	1735477	523093	1121899
589903	841207	660103	24763	906013	1093993	1975243	1339903	1158799	841207	660103	24763	906013	1093993	1975243	1339903	1158799	841207	660103	24763	906013	1093993	1975243	1339903	1158799	1410103
832339	2539	787	1371583	895927	1104079	628423	1999219	1997467	2539	787	1371583	895927	1104079	628423	1999219	1997467	2539	787	1371583	895927	1104079	628423	1999219	1997467	1167667
1500823	1100773	1982077	1885519	103963	1411573	135589	481297	899233	1100773	1982077	1885519	103963	1411573	135589	481297	899233	1100773	1982077	1885519	103963	1411573	135589	481297	899233	499183
1451743	953593	1531147	6247	485827	1879429	1552543	1186789	404449	953593	1531147	6247	485827	1879429	1552543	1186789	404449	953593	1531147	6247	485827	1879429	1552543	1186789	404449	548263
1010683	1595557	468859	1993759	1514179	120577	447463	813217	1046413	1595557	468859	1993759	1514179	120577	447463	813217	1046413	1595557	468859	1993759	1514179	120577	447463	813217	1046413	989323
795727	799063	1518709	114487	1896043	588433	1864417	17929	1200943	799063	1518709	114487	1896043	588433	1864417	17929	1200943	799063	1518709	114487	1896043	588433	1864417	17929	1200943	1204279
302173	1230379	1573813	1033567	954043	1045963	966439	426193	769627	1230379	1573813	1033567	954043	1045963	966439	426193	769627	1230379	1573813	1033567	954043	1045963	966439	426193	769627	1697833
493777	1476913	264529	1570099	1244029	755977	429907	1735477	523093	1476913	264529	1570099	1244029	755977	429907	1735477	523093	1476913	264529	1570099	1244029	755977	429907	1735477	523093	1506229
1308313	841207	660103	24763	906013	1093993	1975243	1339903	1158799	841207	660103	24763	906013	1093993	1975243	1339903	1158799	841207	660103	24763	906013	1093993	1975243	1339903	1158799	691693
855727	2539	787	1371583	895927	1104079	628423	1999219	1997467	2539	787	1371583	895927	1104079	628423	1999219	1997467	2539	787	1371583	895927	1104079	628423	1999219	1997467	1144279
1519153	1100773	1982077	1885519	103963	1411573	135589	481297	899233	1100773	1982077	1885519	103963	1411573	135589	481297	899233	1100773	1982077	1885519	103963	1411573	135589	481297	899233	480853
1077673	953593	1531147	6247	485827	1879429	1552543	1186789	404449	953593	1531147	6247	485827	1879429	1552543	1186789	404449	953593	1531147	6247	485827	1879429	1552543	1186789	404449	922333
635989	1595557	468859	1993759	1514179	120577	447463	813217	1046413	1595557	468859	1993759	1514179	120577	447463	813217	1046413	1595557	468859	1993759	1514179	120577	447463	813217	1046413	1364017
718813	799063	1518709	114487	1896043	588433	1864417	17929	1200943	799063	1518709	114487	1896043	588433	1864417	17929	1200943	799063	1518709	114487	1896043	588433	1864417	17929	1200943	1281193
1166617	1230379	1573813	1033567	954043	1045963	966439	426193	769627	1230379	1573813	1033567	954043	1045963	966439	426193	769627	1230379	1573813	1033567	954043	1045963	966439	426193	769627	833389
959887	1476913	264529	1570099	1244029	755977	429907	1735477	523093	1476913	264529	1570099	1244029	755977	429907	1735477	523093	1476913	264529	1570099	1244029	755977	429907	1735477	523093	1040119
956713	841207	660103	24763	906013	1093993	1975243	1339903	1158799	841207	660103	24763	906013	1093993	1975243	1339903	1158799	841207	660103	24763	906013	1093993	1975243	1339903	1158799	1043293
1533937	2539	787	1371583	895927	1104079	628423	1999219	1997467	2539	787	1371583	895927	1104079	628423	1999219	1997467	2539	787	1371583	895927	1104079	628423	1999219	1997467	466069
620647	1100773	1982077	1885519	103963	1411573	135589	481297	899233	1100773	1982077	1885519	103963	1411573	135589	481297	899233	1100773	1982077	1885519	103963	1411573	135589	481297	899233	1379359
1488499	953593	1531147	6247	485827	1879429	1552543	1186789	404449	953593	1531147	6247	485827	1879429	1552543	1186789	404449	953593	1531147	6247	485827	1879429	1552543	1186789	404449	511507
1785769	884167	1333777	932677	594697	1463773	905197	1092643	1523293	951943	814543	1697719	1074607	1362349	1127983	1118773	349183	598789	525937	1528237	1033867	505633	741283	339943	1491097	222199

It is **block-bordered prime magic square** of order 26 embedded with prime magic square of order 24. It is composed of **equal sums concentric prime magic square** of order 8. The internal blocks of orders 6 and 4 are also of **equal sums prime magic squares**. In this case the magic squares sums are

$$S_{26 \times 26} := 26000078 \quad S_{24 \times 24} := 24000072 \quad S_{6 \times 6} := 6000018 \quad \text{and} \quad S_{4 \times 4} := 4000012$$

Example 22. Block-Bordered Embedded Prime Magic Square Let's consider a following prime magic square of order 26:

1273309	1490347	906349	1678639	1357927	409987	434179	1643869	846577	1338229	814903	1391413	420367	372829	304723	362443	1608487	1587973	1571707	614527	1024957	1636543	651019	1126663	405949	726163
1429507	607063	910213	395023	1288699	686437	1375729	1326889	803977	1448947	1116889	659353	1380817	1844497	1559479	1265347	1049677	1544479	1428529	650863	715423	359449	875923	516673	189697	570499
603553	951109	1808707	343327	846757	1117279	1588303	753139	1537399	511039	1347553	146527	1048897	887269	1057993	1027687	880603	707293	1643137	1358143	611263	1390489	354463	968959	1112737	1396453
1605277	1273549	405199	1927729	389713	735187	1163629	914239	1327987	1445047	96493	1594807	726457	577573	977629	1072039	739363	1472077	334297	1032679	876817	1506613	966139	1022377	1422433	394729
984253	1610467	314239	892987	798097	309157	1568389	751453	1262713	1310209	1107019	1685767	389539	645019	783247	1674817	385249	1139227	740023	906007	1122133	1707379	325189	1216759	1354987	1015753
704269	586129	1144399	1309117	1592113	1167637	1059823	940183	832369	407893	690889	855607	1413877	631537	1198669	595123	1548619	1587673	1346533	653473	412333	451387	1404883	801337	1368469	1295737
1251667	1588393	1108207	867487	1612609	1241869	710929	1289077	758137	387397	1132519	891799	411613	720319	643243	625627	1033423	549259	1202977	797029	1450747	966583	1374379	1356763	1279687	748339
1407619	1233619	1404163	449629	1018489	1582447	1870507	129499	417559	981517	1550377	595843	766387	1598677	1379629	1410979	1416223	457813	1385383	614623	1542193	583783	589027	620377	401329	592387
362233	1124203	454159	449833	288913	8059	358753	1641253	1991947	1711093	1550173	1545847	875803	430909	1447627	1086559	1323877	1405267	65119	1934887	594739	676129	913447	552379	1569097	1637773
1565287	750157	389989	199729	689797	1690849	431617	1248553	737293	1201909	1800277	1610017	1249849	923449	1282417	501013	292627	860779	1259983	1093999	877873	1614757	1498993	717589	1076557	434719
881197	746869	1117489	1903513	1610293	1264819	836377	1085767	672019	554959	72277	882517	1253137	1149979	198529	1033867	1260643	527929	1665709	967327	1123189	493393	927967	1801477	850027	1118809
969637	909289	1853479	1656679	1153249	882727	411703	1246867	462607	1488967	652453	191299	1090717	780499	1031047	972319	1119403	1292713	356869	641863	1388743	609517	1645543	942013	1219507	1030369
1071907	619189	1089793	1604983	711307	1313569	624277	673117	1196029	551059	883117	1340653	1392943	1810309	440527	734659	950329	455527	571477	1349143	1284583	1640557	1124083	1483333	155509	928099
742219	131059	401809	1343299	1642423	1048009	523207	332779	864307	711889	1394749	1665907	1940599	1333357	1620013	770929	406873	1642279	1005457	1383853	1567999	440677	834013	313333	681253	1257787
807127	891859	918529	1138393	1419589	494077	814603	741283	1242097	1493743	644653	1093063	1108147	618799	808363	1525933	896509	1385179	1372369	881479	321163	623989	912979	1272067	1381207	1192879
930229	1608007	323473	1866679	733519	672103	1152793	1501597	1484467	478243	110623	1676533	391999	745273	1692583	349477	1192369	1307767	820627	938359	1362349	324733	1704343	307423	1254733	1069777
796813	1131883	1393039	572683	1212259	1557607	894973	312553	1587787	434839	1427323	606967	868123	1307077	1208797	643927	975823	354643	788563	1321249	1493677	1066063	1356079	791209	692929	1203193
860143	1482739	1244197	1002433	397543	1086523	1405693	594313	913483	1602463	997573	755809	517267	1076077	305017	924499	836677	947203	577639	1422367	1052803	1163329	1075507	1694989	923929	1139863
1547563	407059	1410553	911437	1670923	489733	879493	1120513	1510273	329083	1088569	589453	1592947	1101253	1166497	1565203	1186789	947803	1375243	624763	1052203	813217	434803	833509	898753	452443
861733	1560883	982867	1272883	405277	703327	245587	1754419	1296679	1594729	727123	1017139	439123	1104613	483163	1341883	817987	805027	1022467	977539	1194979	1182019	658123	1516843	895393	1138273
1126963	1676083	501493	482947	748849	1720429	1469239	530767	279577	1251157	1517059	1498513	323923	1374067	378289	1636729	1248799	1299979	1024663	975343	700027	751207	363277	1621717	625939	873043
797569	1488727	1322887	1579	1565167	442399	1105033	1687453	412219	787747	1998427	677119	511279	324889	1482919	1242643	933943	1645363	1211443	678757	506329	1024183	757363	517087	1675117	1202437
596179	771403	996049	1889383	1266487	1327903	847213	498409	515539	1521763	133327	1003957	1228603	1684099	1746463	295663	807637	692239	1179379	1061647	637657	1675273	1650529	253543	315907	1403827
560179	790927	906943	861613	580417	1505929	1185403	1258723	757909	506263	1355353	1081477	1209079	11779	727939	474073	1103497	614827	627637	1118527	1678843	1376017	1087027	1191643	1988227	1439827
989803	59407	1598197	656707	357583	951997	1476799	1667227	1135699	1288117	605257	334099	1868947	1318753	379993	1229077	1593133	357727	994549	616153	432007	1559329	1165993	1686673	666649	1010203
1273843	509659	1093657	321367	642079	1590019	1565827	356137	1153429	661777	1185103	608593	1579639	1627177	1695283	1637563	391519	412033	428299	1385479	975049	363463	1348987	873343	1594057	726697

It is **block-structured prime magic square** of order 24. It is composed of four equal sums **concentric prime magic squares** of order 12. The internal blocks of orders 10, 8, 6 and 4 are also of **equal sums prime magic squares**. In this case the magic squares sums are

$$S_{26 \times 26} := 26000078 \quad S_{24 \times 24} := 24000072 \quad \text{and} \quad S_{12 \times 12} := 12000036$$

Example 23. Block-Structured Magic Square Let's consider a following prime magic square of order 26:

384673	1665109	696763	1338109	1144939	661777	856939	1590073	272383	1228993	475789	1137733	1546759	1358803	319567	913873	1193617	610567	1608127	626533	1379809	918787	597859	1181767	1608133	682597
1152997	1337779	798823	367027	1333357	500413	1387363	1511533	1629169	494563	980107	659899	847009	754627	415879	1389169	1365733	974383	924727	299623	997933	1245067	652573	1156927	1578019	1245379
1724413	1021123	1551133	847069	1320799	777277	505399	1418449	1165729	825739	588433	978883	275593	1718287	1672927	1549837	279883	1526653	1605427	1376623	578689	786349	778507	518059	327079	281719
720319	767317	839029	338347	735307	1369099	1522387	372943	1037929	1624009	1160977	1232689	1279687	602677	1044019	950527	820627	1433149	869179	499189	744823	1356907	1276147	1049479	955987	1397329
1700617	1367953	389629	1189627	492319	270463	1493377	1569187	1174669	810379	1610377	632053	299389	1541809	1642273	590137	1344283	1613329	1118773	1239877	260329	767707	655723	1409869	357733	458197
1644073	1256797	434593	791797	1253803	1094377	598999	1306633	746203	1208209	1565413	743209	355933	1412473	749257	525649	1052287	829867	870517	945409	1184083	1170139	947719	1474357	1250749	587533
1427737	334297	423763	1738183	773659	1212259	1000003	787747	1226347	261823	1576243	1665709	572269	336529	655687	1351663	1483249	812587	1313569	1000003	686437	1187419	516757	648343	1344319	1663477
1187317	917923	1267237	1507993	1654897	693373	1401007	905629	345109	492013	732769	1082083	812689	287107	901339	1526587	456193	511933	815923	1054597	1129489	1488073	1543813	473419	1098667	1712899
897727	264487	1320307	1058077	825337	1729543	506629	430819	1507687	941929	679699	1735519	1102279	1065313	1395943	673117	1119523	1232299	881233	760129	1739677	386677	880483	1326889	604063	934693
1005073	474583	1362763	375997	1264699	630907	477619	1627063	962077	1661659	637243	1525423	994933	1066399	354259	350563	723859	566857	1130827	1500817	1255183	643099	1179379	1649443	1645747	933607
644563	1917667	1411573	1152937	679207	1222729	1494607	581557	834277	1174267	448873	82339	1355443	899917	1746463	1481947	1720123	473353	394579	623383	1421317	1213657	1221499	450169	253543	1100089
57283	1340107	1201183	1632979	666649	1499593	612643	488473	370837	1505443	1019899	662227	1942723	638689	421987	610837	634273	1025623	1075279	1700383	1002073	754939	1347433	843079	1584127	1361317
453247	334897	1303243	661897	855067	1338229	1143067	409933	1727623	771013	1524217	862273	1615333	1317409	1680439	1086133	806389	1389439	391879	1373473	620197	1081219	1402147	818239	391873	641203
1598053	1013227	1472077	1664353	1089799	300073	1365103	921199	1650529	536857	588403	384289	416077	1646563	595579	597049	394249	1034359	1576747	1169713	922717	1329103	1584439	1094809	671533	383179
1650487	891277	1002739	535219	1665247	1026829	792973	1707379	562813	1385827	286513	1143217	349519	343333	1456123	932983	1598953	1120663	739363	1218487	736063	803659	345637	1506559	541543	1656673
466069	901819	1565323	1131553	275323	1602703	1554439	609619	1122133	595717	543217	1098187	1533937	643129	1467589	735739	1242097	995719	492853	1511743	1642423	254833	882517	1242103	532417	1356877
932257	1189453	949699	1239517	1716889	265729	894193	702613	1709473	471607	1050307	810553	1067749	838693	1378999	1074847	1073239	329143	942727	1409407	1516279	998017	731209	925159	621007	1161313
497587	435349	991633	1191409	517267	1114213	329473	1343743	1695319	808597	1008373	1564657	1502419	901333	1366627	966817	1219003	1600069	1504417	474049	1241407	180073	781003	1033189	633379	1098673
423667	727159	945457	1382419	1258753	1418917	255919	1325173	741253	617587	1054549	1272847	1576339	1427323	1123777	1142959	618859	559243	1247479	290317	1462213	1440763	1381147	857047	876229	572683
809023	1180423	373393	300967	1407619	906259	1000003	1093747	592387	1699039	1626613	819583	1190983	987997	1054903	891799	399403	676807	1214737	1000003	785269	1323199	1600603	1108207	945103	1012009
257539	878173	1678717	541777	1511689	674833	1744087	581089	488317	1458229	321289	1121833	1742467	273643	658123	1571467	580807	343963	537793	1709689	752527	1656043	1419199	428539	1341883	1726363
528373	1031809	494917	815533	304687	885793	1670533	656263	1482739	1184473	1505089	968197	1471633	1724557	519097	1546453	1839913	1819933	495589	1525957	758599	399937	160093	453553	1480909	275449
1289077	1219453	544099	1528399	283117	1734277	1105813	1297393	290533	760489	1455907	780553	710929	486349	420073	312043	1268797	1670863	1057279	590599	483727	1001989	926767	1687963	1579933	1513657
1583509	1688329	1456789	868453	1724683	397303	445567	1390387	877873	1404289	434683	311677	416497	1687489	96259	757903	757909	1004287	1507153	488263	357583	1745173	1117489	1264267	1903747	312517
1380469	856789	997267	1464787	334759	973177	1207033	292627	1437193	614179	1713493	1108729	619537	422803	1458463	1067023	401053	879343	1260643	781519	1263943	1196347	1654369	493447	543883	1577203
1583929	986779	527929	335653	910207	1699933	634903	1078807	349477	1463149	1411603	1615717	401953	1616827	1404427	1402957	1605757	965647	423259	830293	1077289	670903	415567	905197	1328473	353443

It is **block-structured prime magic square** of order 26 composed of four equal sums **single-layer bordered prime magic squares** of order 13. In each block of order 13 there is a fixed repeated prime in the inner part i.e., 1000003. This allows us to find **equal sum** blocks of order 13. In this case the magic squares sums are

$$S_{26 \times 26} := 26000078 \text{ and } S_{13 \times 13} := 13000039$$

Example 24. Concentric Single-Layer Bordered Prime Magic Square Let's consider a following prime magic square of order 26:

252401	398249	321617	163733	336761	145829	168347	494927	63131	481673	249881	379187	449759	448907	390113	159389	83813	990797	954869	933551	974417	985379	997391	999983	999683	176213
471281	709817	54101	467549	94379	470651	13187	488981	218783	482519	304757	403757	142421	184721	354581	430799	440087	836807	954509	997889	951407	994199	995927	996539	11633	528719
188417	395189	289127	161753	239699	15671	287867	499679	412289	266153	66161	438953	126683	123203	126359	686339	967229	979949	826349	973151	989909	999431	999029	525017	604811	811583
69491	301583	496841	550757	119447	355799	73331	304631	376709	44519	69911	181439	250751	292427	967763	348353	971561	997961	852239	978821	996461	969929	297191	503159	698417	930509
130223	114041	77783	211811	199103	368939	382463	319811	87911	480587	467261	308051	423257	405047	472247	79601	849917	955313	979061	979211	999773	242447	788189	922217	885959	869777
150869	239711	335417	253823	247799	415697	422453	281993	198659	164987	154613	430427	147377	460337	357989	915623	969863	990323	915869	997589	176201	752201	746177	664583	760289	849131
326549	123407	21383	275921	255083	212183	799343	149867	64661	221603	23357	81233	145967	889937	901133	942749	774491	905453	976883	123323	787817	744917	724079	978617	876593	673451
436979	493001	302873	58229	341057	423209	54269	109001	192617	318161	246473	173429	133877	460829	836117	948581	996323	975083	609509	945731	576791	658943	941771	697127	506999	563021
218117	208889	149519	330689	362291	274019	352349	22643	124067	382763	251117	157841	421559	24419	982061	959723	783599	912851	977357	647651	725981	637709	669311	850481	791111	781883
121403	478637	182681	172259	354479	238991	113489	70997	19841	35801	71129	156089	167543	620657	997649	957701	993431	980159	929003	886511	761009	645521	827741	817319	521363	878597
39869	70439	428411	151703	299567	14723	266177	352511	157721	466073	881591	86783	124739	940271	457889	508727	533927	842279	647489	733823	985277	700433	848297	571589	929561	960131
140333	98573	109541	304553	31091	163847	30539	120299	364433	29201	149057	306191	65951	934049	693809	850943	970799	635567	879701	969461	836153	968909	695447	890459	901427	859667
41957	311237	48869	341597	89381	41513	2903	65921	447683	979373	194963	878651	799619	200381	121349	805037	20627	552317	934079	997097	958487	910619	658403	951131	688763	958043
80681	94049	91529	400523	282011	12413	277757	989939	804191	790379	349709	517901	808553	191447	482099	650291	209621	195809	10061	722243	987587	717989	599477	908471	905951	919319
428951	480419	222269	125201	441527	876077	982769	919823	997973	919067	933407	297257	325877	674123	702743	66593	80933	2027	80177	17231	123923	558473	874799	777731	519581	571049
490277	310043	993401	912083	867467	933209	812627	963701	998381	773537	491273	913217	875261	59729	542111	118409	226463	1619	36299	187373	66791	132533	87917	6599	689957	509723
926027	438233	829877	229127	926567	572927	782501	997793	998561	6569	928871	843911	832457	379343	2351	42299	964199	1439	2207	217499	427073	73433	770873	170123	561767	73973
754739	287501	951389	984119	556709	998633	705821	996881	87149	617237	748883	842159	578441	975581	17939	40277	216401	875933	3119	294179	1367	443291	15881	48611	712499	245261
948551	904847	994769	995747	997121	999239	942779	390491	807383	681839	753527	826571	866123	539171	163883	51419	3677	24917	890999	57221	761	2879	4253	5231	95153	51449
976187	987083	999863	999491	998681	999521	876677	850133	935339	778397	976643	918767	854033	110063	98867	57251	225509	94547	23117	200657	479	1319	509	137	12917	23813
996329	989687	999917	999749	992513	823799	577547	718007	801341	835013	845387	569573	852623	539663	642011	84377	30137	9677	84131	2411	584303	7487	251	83	10313	3671
998969	994013	999959	999809	757553	631061	617537	680189	912089	519413	532739	691949	576743	594953	527753	920399	150083	44687	20939	20789	227	800897	191	41	5987	1031
991217	992891	999599	702809	880553	644201	926669	695369	623291	955481	930089	818561	749249	707573	32237	651647	28439	2039	147761	21179	3539	30071	449243	401	7109	8783
999359	988343	474983	838247	760301	984329	712133	500321	587711	733847	933839	561047	873317	876797	873641	313661	32771	20051	173651	26849	10091	569	971	710873	11657	641
997037	988367	945899	532451	905621	529349	986813	511019	781217	517481	695243	596243	857579	815279	645419	569201	559913	163193	45491	2111	48593	5801	4073	3461	290183	2963
823787	601751	678383	836267	663239	854171	831653	505073	936869	518327	750119	620813	550241	551093	609887	840611	916187	9203	45131	66449	25583	14621	2609	17	317	747599

It is **concentric single-layer bordered prime magic square** of order 26. The internal prime magic squares of orders 24 is also a **single-layer bordred prime magic squarë** of order 24 as given in Example ??. In this case the magic square sum is

$$S_{26 \times 26} := 26000078$$

4 Author's Contribution to Recreation of Numbers and Magic Squares

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- (ii) **Inder J. Taneja**, Magic Squares - <https://numbers-magic.com/?cat=3>. Also for the publications on magic squares see the link: <https://numbers-magic.com/?p=668>.

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• Block-Wise Magic Squares

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